

Deliverable Report

Analysis and experimental validation of revised draft of testing procedures, experience from all tested electrolysers

(D5.6)

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Abbreviations and Indices

Abbreviation	Explanation
AC	Alternating current
aFRR	Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve: FRR that can be activated by an automatic control device. ¹
BOP	Balance of plant
C&CS	Control and Communication System
DC	Direct current
FCR	Frequency Containment Reserve: The active power reserves available to contain system frequency after the occurrence of an imbalance. ¹
FRR	Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve: The Active Power Reserves available to restore System Frequency to the Nominal Frequency, and for Synchronous Area consisting of more than one Load Frequency Control (LFC) Area to restore power balance to the scheduled value. ¹
GS	Grid Services
HMI	Human machine interface
HTO	Hydrogen transmitted to oxygen
mFRR	Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve. ¹
OTH	Oxygen transmitted to hydrogen
RR	Replacement Reserve: The active power reserves available to restore or support the required level of FRR to be prepared for additional system imbalances, including operating reserves. ¹
FHa	Aragon Hydrogen Foundation, a research organisation
IHT	Industrie Haute Technologie, an electrolyser manufacturer
DTU	Danish Technical University
ITM	ITM Power Plc, an electrolyser manufacturer
NEL	NEL Hydrogen, an electrolyser manufacturer
DLR	German Aerospace Center, a research organisation

¹ Definition provided in D2.1 based on ENTSOE glossary

1 Summary

Updated testing protocols for electrolyzers performing grid services were submitted as the QualyGridS report D2.4. These testing protocols and data evaluation procedures were applied to the alkaline and PEM electrolyser systems in the project. The following reports, of which this report gives the publically accessible information, are to show the results, report about the qualifications of the systems or the gaps to qualification, feedback to protocol improval and special aspects tested with each system. This report gives the results obtained with PEM and alkaline electrolyser systems from 10 kW to 1 MW size, in a test bench or a real system environment.

A 10 kW alkaline electrolyser at FHa proved fast enough to pass the FCR first test criteria and showed only small deviations in the FRR and RR tests due to current control instead of power control.

The test methods for first method of FCR, aFRR and mFRR were validated at IHT site for a 50 kW alkaline electrolyser. The electrolyser has successfully passed these tests and the qualification criteria.

The aggregated aFRR and mFRR testing protocol was applied to a 300 kW alkaline electrolyser at NEL. The system was power controlled and passed the required criteria.

A 28kW PEM electrolyser system of ITM was installed in a test bench at DTU. The system showed power increase from standby or low power to nominal power within approx. 1 sec considering the stack power, with slower reaction considering the total system power. It can be concluded from the tests that FCR and FRR services can be operated if a power control and a suitable interface for power setpoint input are installed.

A 50 kW PEM electrolyser system at DLR installed in a refueling station environment turned out to be of too much experimental nature and even if considering only the stack power for grid service too slow for some services and with a control not fulfilling the requirements as implemented now.

A 1 MW PEM electrolyser system feeding hydrogen into the gas grid showed only small deviations to the grid service requirements that could easily be improved if this application was favourized.

So in principle modern alkaline and PEM electrolyser systems' technology is ready for grid services. For some improvements in power control and with input ports for power set point signals they would even improve the performance.

It turned out that the revised draft of testing protocols could well be applied and provides the required results. Only few changes were recommended. The finalized testing protocols which are publically accessible and differ little from the draft D2.4 analyzed in this report can be accessed².

2 Introduction

The tests run on the second draft of testing protocols D2.4 focus mostly on the differences from the first set of testing protocols D2.1 and on getting the information about the qualification of the electrolyser investigated for grid services. While for most tests themselves there is little difference to the first draft notably the data evaluation was changed. Also some aggregated tests integrating several tests into one longer sequence were newly designed as an alternative to running the single shorter tests. The purpose of the second round of testing, about which this deliverable report informs, was

² QualyGridS D2.5 "Qualifying tests of electrolyzers for grid services", DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937273>

- to evaluate the testing protocols and give feedback if improvements or clarifications are needed in the final version of testing protocols in deliverable report D2.5 “Finalized testing protocol”
- to verify the suitability of the investigated electrolyzers for grid services
- to identify possible needs for further development for today’s PEM electrolyser systems to perform grid services in the future
- to find out which grid service is best fitting the electrolyzers’ properties.

The publically available information on the first round of testing based on the first draft of testing protocols D2.1 was published in a scientific paper³. Much of this information is still relevant here.

The electrolyser systems used for analysing the testing protocols are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Basic electrical parameters of QalyGridSelectrolyzers and test benches

	DTU	DLR	FHa	IHT	NEL
Nominal Power of the tested electrolyzers	28kW	50kW	10kW	50 kW	300kW
Electrolyser type	PEM	PEM	Alkaline	Alkaline	Alkaline
BOP power	<1kW	<4kW	3.3kW	<1kW	2-3kW
Supply voltage	3 x 400V,50Hz				
DC stack voltage	0-13V	0-17	0-18 V	0-18 V	0-250V
DC Stack current	0-3000A	0-3000A	0-3500A	0-10.000A	0-1600A

In addition results from a 1 MW PEM electrolyser system were analysed based on QalyGridS testing protocols.

3 Reports Experiments

3.1 10 kW alkaline electrolyser at FHa

3.1.1 Description of the 10 kW alkaline electrolyser system, the test setup, the interfaces, changes to the original electrolyser to perform the tests

The 10 kW alkaline electrolyser investigated at FHa consists of a stack manufactured by IHT and a system and test bench built up at FHa. Technical data is given in table 1.

³ Shi You, Regine Reissner , Christoph Imboden , Cyril Bourasseau , Pablo Marcuello , Daniel Greenhalgh , Ben Green , Laura Abadía , Vanesa Gil , Marius Bornstein , Yi Zong , Xu Chen, Chresten Træholt, “Facilitating Water Electrolyzers for Electricity GridServices in Europe through Establishing Standardized Testing Protocols”, Clean Energy, accepted for publication, 6. August 2020

Figure 1 *FHa test bench for alkaline electrolyzers*

The system is current controlled. The test bench allows up to 60 bar and 95°C, with power up to 25 kW and hydrogen production up to 3.5 Nm³/h. The data acquisition rate is typically 1 Hz, up to 10 Hz for power measurement⁴.

The test was carried out assuming that P_{low} and P_{up} correspond to I_{low} and I_{up} and P_{med} (for FCR test) has been calculated considering the expression given by the protocol $0.5 \cdot (P_{up} + P_{low})$. In contrast to the previous validation of this protocol done based on D2.1, power at the rectifier (understood as AC power input) and BOP power consumption have been measured and registered with 10 Hz resolution.

3.1.2 Applying 2nd draft testing protocols (D2.4) to 10 kW alkaline electrolyser system

3.1.2.1 FCR First method

Figure 2 *FCR first method*

⁴ L. Abadia, presentation at QualyGridS final workshop, https://www.qualygrids.eu/publications/4-electrolyzers_alkaline_laura_abadia_fha_qualygrids/

Figure 2 shows test results for FCR first method. The measured power at the rectifier input is shown as P_rect. The upper and lower limits of the permitted range at the constant power sections of the protocol is also shown. P_bop is the power consumption of the system and test station BOP which, for a small system as this made for laboratory and research applications, is very high and fluctuating as compared to the stack/rectifier power consumption. Therefore the the protocol is applied and evaluated with taking the rectifier input power for grid service, an option given in the testing protocols.

Table 1. Power stability in the phases of FCR protocol

Power stability when no grid service is provided

	Maximum deviation value [$P_{med}=0.5*(P_{up}+P_{low})$]	Maximum deviation value [P_{med} time averaged]
KPI	0.7 %	0.73%

Power stability at P_{up} (phases B and D):

	Maximum deviation value P_{up} time averaged
KPI	2.1%

Power stability at P_{low} (phases F and H):

	Maximum deviation value - KPI - P_{low} time averaged
KPI	1.0 %

- Duration of ramps:

Ramps up			Ramps down		
	Initial response time	Ramp duration (t_{full})		Initial response time	Ramp duration (t_{full})
2	0.11 sec	3 sec	3	0.9 sec	5 sec
4	0.11 sec	4 sec	5	0.5 sec	4 sec
7	0.2 sec	2 sec	6	0.5 sec	3 sec
9	0.8 sec	3 sec	8	0 sec	2 sec

Ramp n° 5:

Ramp n° 6:

Figure 3 Duration and initial response time for some of the ramps of FCR 1st method at FHa. (ramps 2, 5, 6)

Therefore, the system meets the requirements of FCR first method.

3.1.2.2 FCR Second method

The second test of the FCR protocol has been tested at FHa collecting power data every 100 millisecond.

The system is current controlled.

Numbers there are given in % of the control power range with 0 % corresponding to P_{low} , 50% corresponding to P_{med} and 100% corresponding to P_{up} . Based on our system, this has been translated to 0% being I_{low} , 50% being I_{med} and 100% being I_{up} .

Figure 4 *FCR second method. current vs time figures obtained with an internal script that pretends to give the setpoints in 1 sec intervals 3) compilation of the current profiles: from script, set point, measured, upper current limit and lower current limit..power can be registered every 10 Hz or faster but the C&CS controls and monitors the operation and the rest of parameters every 1 Hz.*

In contrast to FCR 1st method, although command changes happen very quickly in the FCR 2nd method protocol the amplitude of the variations are considerably smaller. 75% of the setpoints are in the interval 30-70% of P_{up} which has meant that the power consumption of the BoP does not show periods with clear different power consumption.

3.1.2.3 Aggregated aFRR test

As the system is current controlled, the test was carried out assuming that P_{low} and P_{up} correspond to I_{low} and I_{up} .

The current setpoint and the duration of the ramps were set in a .csv file and loaded into the C&CS before starting the test thus the instructions “wait for system power to stabilize” were assumed to be 5 minutes

Figure 5 Aggregated aFRR test protocol. Power (%) vs time. Purple and green horizontal lines indicate the limits $\pm 5\%$ ($P_{up}-P_{low}$). Dotted lines represent the theoretical power expected based on a linear correlation.

Figure 6 800-second 0-100 % ramp-ups and ramp-downs

Figure 7 300-second and 133-second ramp-ups and ramp-downs

For FHa test bench power usually overpasses its target value for few minutes before going down and get stable.

3.1.2.4 Aggregated mFRR test

As the system is current controlled, the test was carried out assuming that P_{low} and P_{up} correspond to I_{low} and I_{up}

Figure 8 Aggregated mFRR test protocol. Power (%) vs time. Purple and green horizontal lines indicate the limits $\pm 5\%$ ($P_{up}-P_{low}$). Dotted lines represent the theoretical power expected based on a linear correlation

Figure 9 Power tolerance during the ramps.

The 30 minutes said by the protocol have been enough to reach a stable value of current, voltage and power. The purity of the oxygen line has also met its stabilized value.

1- Reduction of the duration of the ramps to 10 minutes instead of 900 seconds (D2.1)

It has been observed at FHa that power overpasses the target value more abruptly with ramps of 600 seconds instead of 900 seconds for the case of power variation from 0%_{up} to 100%. The destabilization has remained inside the range limited by $\pm 5\%(P_{up}-P_{low})$.

3.1.2.5 Aggregated RR protocol

As the system is current controlled, the test was carried out assuming that P_{low} and P_{up} correspond to I_{low} and I_{up} .

Figure 10 Aggregated RR testing protocol

Power stability during activation

Phase	Max. deviation value at Pup	% of data points outside the interval $P_{up} \pm 5\%(P_{up}-P_{low})$	Max. deviation value at Plow	% of data points outside the interval $P_{low} \pm 5\%(P_{up}-P_{low})$
B	0.64%	0%	0.17%	0%

Table3. RR - Power deviation between Power achieved and target power

	Power deviation from target power Deviation (%)	Inside ($\pm 5\%$ (Pup-Plow))?
Step 3	1,76%	YES
Step 6	5,97%	NO
Step 11	7,12%	NO
Step 16	5,25%	NO
Step 21	0,00%	YES
Step 24	0,51%	YES
Step 26	2,24%	YES
Step 29	2,58%	YES
Step 34	4,45%	YES
Step 39	3,74%	YES
Step 44	0,00%	YES
Step 47	2,86%	YES

Test current setpoints have been introduced manually by the operator as steps commands and it has been observed that the target value has been reached in less than 5 seconds (t_{full} below 5 seconds).

3.1.3 Conclusions on tests at 10 kW alkaline electrolyser

The protocols selected for testing have been those with the biggest modifications in their definition as compared to the first draft of testing protocols and those elaborated as an aggregated version.

The results obtained have shown that the modifications introduced are acceptable as they do not influence the test benches' performance and also beneficial as they reduce the protocol's duration which helps to increase the willingness of potential users of these protocols. The decrease of time not only makes it more practical to carry out the tests but also to reduce the associated costs.

FHa's system has shown to be able to run the FCR first method, Requirements of FRR have not been always met for FHa test bench. This would be solved with the implementation of the power control mode as planned for systems participating in GS.

The aggregated version of the protocols is a very good approach to condense and simplify the methodology to evaluate the system's adequacy to provide grid services.

3.2 The 50 kW alkaline electrolyser at IHT

3.2.1 Description of the 50 kW alkaline electrolyser system, the test setup, the interfaces, changes to the original electrolyser to perform the tests

The 50 kW alkaline electrolyser investigated at IHT consists of a stack and system manufactured by IHT. Technical data is given in table 1. The test bench has been operated between 10 and 100% load, being 50 kW (approx.) what it is measured at power electronics side when unit is operated at 100% load

3.2.2 Applying 2nd draft testing protocols (D2.4) to 50 kW alkaline electrolyser system

3.2.2.1 FCR first test

Figure 11 FCR first method – IHT test bench

The FCR first test was applied to the IHT alkaline electrolyser and data processed.(Figure 11)

- Duration of ramps:

Ramps up			Ramps down		
	Ramp duration (t_m)	Ramp duration (t_{full})		Ramp duration (t_m)	Ramp duration (t_{full})
2	8 sec	13 sec	3	2 sec	3 sec
4	8 sec	14 sec	5	7 sec	13 sec
7	2 sec	4 sec	6	3 sec	12 sec
9	10 sec	14 sec	8	5 sec	13 sec

Figure 12 Ramp duration and response time (ramps 2, 3, 6 and 7)

Therefore, the system meets the requirements of FCR first method.

3.2.2.2 aFRR aggregated test

Figure 13 Aggregated aFRR test protocol at IHT test bench.

Figure 14 800-second ramp-ups

Figure 15 800-second 0-100 % ramp-ups and ramp-downs

Figure 16 800-second ramp-downs

Figure 17 300-second and 133-second ramp-ups and ramp-downs

The figures show the data evaluation for the various sections of the testing protocol comparing the measured power to the permitted range of deviation. As it can be seen the power in the constant power section is always inside the range. For the ramps very few deviations are observed, below the amount of deviations permitted. Therefore it can be stated that this electrolyser is passing the requirements for aFRR grid service.

3.2.2.3 Aggregated mFRR test

Figure 18 Aggregated mFRR test protocol at IHT test bench.

Figure 19 *Negative control ramps up to 25, 50, 75 and 100%. Aggregated mFRR test protocol at IHT test bench.*

Figure 20 *Positive control ramps down to 25, 50, 75 and 100%. Aggregated mFRR test protocol at IHT test bench.*

Figure 21 *Positive ramp after being constant for 1 hour. Aggregated mFRR test protocol at IHT test bench.*

Figure 22 *Negative ramp after being constant for 1 hour. Aggregated mFRR test protocol at IHT test bench.*

As the measurements and evaluation show the electrolyser also passes the criteria for mFRR grid service.

3.2.3 Conclusions

The test methods for first method of FCR and aFRR and mFRR aggregated tests were validated at IHT site. The electrolyser has successfully passed these tests and the qualification criteria.

3.3 300 kW alkaline electrolyser at NEL

3.3.1 Description of the 300 kW alkaline electrolyser system, the test setup, the interfaces, changes to the original electrolyser to perform the tests

An alkaline electrolyser with a 300 kW stack of manufacturer NEL was tested at the NEL test facility in Notodden, Norway. Current and power control of the system was alternatively implemented and tested. Data logging and set point were implemented with a frequency of 10 Hz⁵.

3.3.2 Applying 2nd draft testing protocols (D2.4) to 300 kW PEM electrolyser system

3.3.2.1 Aggregated automatic FRR (aFRR) and manual FRR (mFRR) testing protocol

Several testing protocols were applied. As an example here the results of the aFRR and mFRR tests are presented.

Figure 23 Top: Illustration of the ramp protocol and the logged ramp protocol. Bottom: Deviation between real power and power setpoint and a boxplot of the deviation. The percentages in the boxplot are the relative time inside and outside of the $\pm 5\%$ region.

The protocol remained inside of the $\pm 5\%$ range more than 95 % of the time in the periods of constant power. Spikes outside of the $\pm 5\%$ are preset at instant and fast power changes. The instant (yellow) transitions shall not be evaluated. All the logged ramps in the protocol and a $\pm 2.5\%$ region is plotted below. The “outer” envelope is delayed 20 seconds. From a visual inspection all the real power values are inside of the envelope.

⁵ L. Abadia et al., presentation at QualyGridS final workshop, https://www.qualygrids.eu/publications/4-electrolyzers_alkaline_laura_abadia_fha_qualygrids/

Figure 24 *The logged ramps in the protocol and a $\pm 2.5\%$ region plotted. The “outer” envelope is delayed 20 seconds. From a visual inspection all the real power values are inside of the envelope.*

3.3.3 Conclusions

Testing of the Frequency Restoration Reserve (FRR) and Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) was done with a 10 Hz control and log system. All protocols were run using power control implemented using an external feedback from a NEMO power meter and a PID regulator in LabVIEW controlling the USB-6215 analog I/O unit.

The same power level could be used for all the FRR protocols. Hence the aggregated automatic FRR (aFRR) and manual FRR (mFRR) testing protocol was used. The protocol remained inside of the $\pm 5\%$ range 99.8 % of the time in the periods of constant power. This is inside of the required 95 %. All the ramps in the protocols were analyzed by plotting the setpoint, logged values and requirement envelopes. 22 of the 22 ramps were inside of the requirement envelopes.

Variations in primarily temperature will in a current controlled system make the power deviate or drift. The implementation of power control was keeping the power at a constant level during the 10+ hour protocol.

3.4 ITM / DTU 28 kW PEM electrolyser system

3.4.1 Description of the 28 kW PEM electrolyser system, the test setup, the interfaces, changes to the original electrolyser to perform the tests

The system applied to testing is a scaled-down prototype from ITM POWER Inc., as shown in Figure 25. The 28 kW electrolyser system was first installed in August 2018, and tested for the QualyGridS project from time to time.

Figure 25 The 35kW ITM PEM electrolyser system installed at DTU's test bench and its configuration at DTU

The system by default has two options to regulate its power consumption,

1. HMI manual controller: a default manual control solution of the electrolyser system, allowing for manual change of DC current set-point and DC voltage
2. HMI profile controller: a default automated control solution of the electrolyser system, allowing for execution of a profile of time series DC current set-points with maximum 20 time steps and minimum 1 min interval between each time step,

In order to fulfil the testing requirements, e.g. automated control on a second basis, DTU and ITM have developed an additional control loop, so-called "macro script controller". The controller converts frequency/power reference signals into DC current setpoints and input to the setpoints to the HMI interface by emulating manual input actions on the second level of resolution. The control solution developed is not optimal yet in comparison with the original test bench proposal. One observed issue of the macro script controller is a time delay. Every time when a control signal was generated by the controller and sent to the HMI, a time delay was created due to windows system scheduling. Although its value is uncertain, the value of a single delay is relatively small. However, for tests that require frequency power variation or many times of changing setpoints, the cumulative error can be big. Table 4 provides an overview of what control solutions were applied to different protocols and the observed issues.

The test bench for the system was set up at DTU using the lab's cooling system, DI water supply, the possibilities of gas venting available there and other input and output to the system.

Table 4: An overview of test protocol implementation

Protocol	Controller	controller resolution	Comment
FCR_1	HMI profile controller	every 1 min	Implementation is slightly different from the protocol.
Aggregated mFRR	Macro script controller	every 30 sec	The test was performed as two individual tests due to interruptions experienced in the middle of the test.

In Figure 26, the points of measurements of the PEM test bench are illustrated. During the test, AC power measured as grid supply and the DC power measured as rectifier out/stack input are recorded and used for evaluation.

Figure 26 Points of measurement of the test bench

3.4.2 Applying 2nd draft testing protocols (D2.4) to 28 kW PEM electrolyser system

3.4.2.1 Characterisation test

Determination of start-up time from standby mode:

Figure 27 System startup from standby to nominal current (2200 A). (a) DC power rectifier output, (b) grid power input to the entire system⁶

The start-up time from standby mode protocol was tested on the electrolyser, with the results given in Figure 27. From the stack side, after triggering the start button, the system current goes to the setpoint within 1 second, as shown in Figure 27(a). From Figure 27(a), the power becomes lower than nominal power by -5% after about 23 minutes. This issue can be solved if a power controller is available. If this issue is not considered, the start-up time from standby mode can roughly be calculated as

$$\tau_{standby \rightarrow start_DC} = 1 \text{ sec}$$

From the grid side, after triggering the start button, the system power goes to the setpoint in about 205 seconds, as shown in Figure 27(b). The same issue in terms of power stability can be observed. If this issue is disregarded or fixed by implementing a power controller, the start-up time from standby mode can roughly be calculated as

$$\tau_{standby \rightarrow start_AC} = 205 \text{ sec}$$

3.4.2.2 FCR first test

In this test, because the control applied has a minimum resolution of 1min, the test protocol was implemented slightly different from the protocol given in D2.4. Figure 28 illustrates the differ-

⁶ B. Green, presentation at QualyGridS final workshop, https://www.qualygrids.eu/publications/5-electrolyzers_pem_ben_green_itm_qualygrids/

rence, i.e., the duration implemented for maintaining P_{up} , P_{med} and P_{low} are rounded to minutes. In addition, current signals are used as alternative to power signals. During the test, the P_{up} is defined as 2200A stack current and the P_{low} is defined as 200A stack current, with which P_{med} can be calculated as 1200A.

Figure 28 Reference profile of test signals. (a) given in protocol; (b) implemented

Results of the test are presented in Figure 29, including both the DC power consumed by the stack and the AC power consumed by the system. From the stack side, as illustrated in Figure 29(a), the average P_{up} measured at 2200A is 22.96kW. The average P_{med} at 1200A is 11.37kW, and the average P_{low} at 200A is 1.64kW. From the grid side, as illustrated in Figure 28(b), the average P_{up} at 2200A is 28.56kW. The average P_{med} at 1200A is 14.23kW, and the average P_{low} at 200A is 4.1kW.

(b)

Figure 29 Testing results of FCR first test. (a) Measured rectifier output in DC power; (b) Measured grid power supply in AC power. Note. Permissible range indicated as $\pm 5\%$ of $P_{med} - P_{low}$.

Performance evaluation:

The results are evaluated w.r.t. both power stability and ramps, according to the test protocol.

Power stability:

As illustrated in Figure 29, wherein the permissible range of deviation is set as $\pm 5\%$ of the power difference between P_{med} and P_{low} , the DC power fails to pass the criteria at Phase B, i.e., when the electrolyser operated at P_{up} for the 1st time and pass the criteria in all rest phases. Regarding the AC power, the electrolyser failed to pass the criteria at phase C, i.e., when the electrolyser operated at P_{med} for the 2nd time.

Ramp:

For the DC side, all (up and down) ramps are within 1 second, the results measured at the AC side are summarized in the table below. The longest ramp up duration is 160 second when the system ramped from P_{med} to P_{up} for the 2nd time. The longest ramp down duration is 71 second when the system ramped from P_{med} to P_{low} for the 1st time.

Table 5 Ramp duration measured from grid side for FCR first test

	(a) P_{med} to P_{up}	(b) P_{up} to P_{med}	(c) P_{med} to P_{low}	(d) P_{low} to P_{med}
t_{m1}	78 sec	3 sec	36 sec	59 sec
t_{full1}	156 sec	7 sec	71 sec	118 sec
t_{m2}	83 sec	31 sec	1.5 sec	76 sec
t_{full2}	160 sec	63 sec	3 sec	153sec

Initial response time:

During the test, data measured from the rectifier and from the grid side are logged separately. The rectifier out logged by an Agilent data log instrument that directly writes into a USB disk, grid input data logged by the microSCADA system. As the data logging for the rectifier output is 1Hz, the initial response time for the side of rectifier output must be faster than 1 sec. The initial response time measured from the grid side is less than 5 sec. However, because the clock of the two data logging systems are not synchronized, the real value for the initial response time measured from the grid side might be longer.

Summary of evaluation (based on measured AC power consumption of the whole electrolyser system, incl. BOP):

Performance indicator	Symbol	The measured value	TSO's requirement
Ramp duration	t_m	83 sec (max)	≤ 15 sec
	t_{full}	160 sec (max)	≤ 30 sec
Stability: maximum deviation	Δ_{max}	0.98kW, which is greater than $0.05(P_{med} - P_{low})$	$\leq 0.05(P_{med} - P_{low})$
Initial response time	t_{init}	approx. 1-5 sec	≤ 1.5 sec
Percentage of data points outside the envelope for FCR first test		0.54% ⁷	0%

$P_{low_system}=4.1kW$ $P_{med_system}=14.23kW$ $P_{up_sys}=28.56kW$

3.4.2.3 mFRR aggregated test

Figure 30 illustrates aggregated mFRR test profile defined by the protocol, and the corresponding current setpoints which were applied to regulate the power consumption of the electrolyser with a 30 seconds interval.

Figure 30 Reference profile of test signals. (a) given in protocol; (b) implemented current setpoints

⁷ The value corresponds to the percentage of data points outside the $\pm 0.05(P_{med} - P_{low})$ deviation range.

Due to technical failures experienced during the test, e.g. malfunctioning of the repatriation pump, insufficient cooling capacity, interrupted water supply etc., the test was implemented as two separate tests.

Results of the tests are given in Figure 31. During the test, P_{up} is defined as a DC current command that equals to 2200A, P_{low} is defined as a DC current command that equals to 1A. The ramp is calculated linearly according to the P_{up} , the P_{low} and ramp time. Because of the stack voltage variation at different currents, the stack power is not exactly linear with the current. Further, as illustrated in Figure 31a, there is a spike happened during the system start. After the start-up, the system power of P_{low} was not maintained stably (such as the power dip before the 1st controlled ramping) due to the process of start-up and the very low current setpoint. According to experience learned when testing D2.1d, this issue could be avoided by either operating the system at a medium/high load for some time before operating at a very low power or increasing the low current to a higher value, such as 200A.

The measured P_{up} and P_{low} mean values are as follows:

Stack side $P_{up_DC}=22.7$ kW
Stack side $P_{low_DC}=0.00622$ kW
Grid side $P_{up_AC}=28.48$ kW
Grid side $P_{low_AC}=1.85$ kW

During the period of constant power, the maximum absolute deviations between the measured value and the mean value are as follows:

Stack side $\Delta P_{DC_max} = 1.25$ kW, which is greater than 5% of $P_{up_DC} - P_{low_DC}$
Grid side, $\Delta P_{AC_max} = 1.35$ kW, which is greater than 5% of $P_{up_AC} - P_{low_AC}$

The above evaluation was performed when the results of the two separate tests were all taken into account while excluding the overlapped period. However, when the two tests were evaluated separately, both of them could pass the criteria for constant power.

(a)

(b)

Figure 31 *Testing results of aggregated mFRR which was implemented as two separate tests (a) and (b), rectifier's DC output is in blue and system's AC input is in red.*

Evaluation regarding the percentage of data points outside the range for constant power periods, and percentage of data points outside the range for the ramps are not conducted. The reason is due to the limitation of the control setup. Although the macro controller invoked by Windows Task Scheduler intends to execute control input every 30s, the real time spent for each interval is not exactly 30s. As time evolves, the difference also increases, which resulted in an accumulated time difference. Therefore, as indicated by Figure 32, such difference does not imply the true difference between the reference current signal and the measured current signal. The issue of unsynchronized clocks when multiple clocks are involved in testbench can be a serious problem for qualification test.

Figure 32 *Difference between the current reference value and the measured value for the 1st part of aggregated mFRR test*

3.4.3 Conclusions

The PEM electrolyser deployed at DTU is a scaled-down system from ITM's commercial electrolyser system with PEM stack shortened to reach a laboratory scale. Therefore, the ratio of BOP power over the stack power of this system may not be the same as that of the commercial system.

Due to resource limitation and a number of technical issues experienced during the test, only a few protocols were managed to be tested with results presented in this report.

The characterisation protocol of startup from standby shows a very fast increase of the DC stack power to reach the nominal current and power within approx. 1 second. The total system's power increase is slower.

The testing protocols described in D2.4 "The revised testing protocols" were applied to test bench at DTU with a 28kW PEM electrolyser system. The test results were logged and analysed with a special focus on if the revision has improved the applicability of the testing protocols. Although only two protocols were tested, i.e., the FCR first test and the aggregated mFRR test, the experience of protocol implementation is satisfactory. In comparison to the first testing protocols draft (D2.1d), the revised protocol is much more user friendly and easy to implement.

During the process of testing, the main technical challenge remains as before, i.e. the limitation of the implemented control system, especially related to unsynchronized clocks when involving multiple measurement instruments and the accumulated delay when using the Macro via Window Task Scheduler to realize real time control. This limitation resulted in significant difficulties in evaluating the system's performance when following a large number of continuous control signals. In principle, a dedicated power controller can solve this problem.

In addition, the process of testing was interrupted and finally stopped by a number of technical issues related to both the testbench and the electrolyser system. It is therefore recommended that some future efforts shall be allocated to improving testbench design in order to increase its levels of reliability and reduce the level of human intervention.

3.5 DLR / Hydrogenics 50 kW PEM electrolyser system

3.5.1 Description of the 50 kW PEM electrolyser system, the test setup, the interfaces, changes to the original electrolyser to perform the tests

The testing protocols were applied to a Hydrogenics 50 kW electrolyser operated at DLR (Figure 34). Model name Large Active Area PEM Electrolyser BOP with PEM Stack Model 1500 E; Hylyzer 10/20 outdoor version.

This PEM electrolyser manufactured by Hydrogenics uses a 6-cell 1500 cm² area stack and can be run up to 2 A/cm². Stack and system concept are built in an equivalent way as for the 1 MW PEM electrolyser operated at Uniper in Hamburg-Reitbrook. However the 50 kW electrolyser can be considered rather as a test bench for the large area short stack and it is by no way an optimized system for an electrolyser with 7.5 Nm³/h hydrogen production.

As compared to the schematic system shown in the testing protocols D2.4 Figure 1 (here **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) the components “make-up water storage”, H₂ buffer and H₂ compressor are not included in this system. For some of the measurements also the component Deoxidizer was not included because it caused system problems and it could not be replaced by one compatible with this system. Different from the scheme shown in Figure 33 the back pressure valve is not downstream of the demister in the hydrogen stream but downstream of the dryer.

The system thoroughly controls many operating parameters. For most of them the system reacts when the allowed parameter range is exceeded and makes an emergency stop: immediate reduction of stack current to 0 A, slow venting of the gases to ambient pressure, alarm.

Figure 33 Schematic system as depicted in Figure 1 of testing protocols D2.1

Figure 34 Container with 50 kW system and surrounding hydrogen infrastructure (top); Short stack with 1500cm² cell area (top small insert); process room (bottom left) with stack and operation room (bottom right) with HMI (Human machine Interface) and DI water processing of 50 kW experimental electrolyser used at DLR

Figure 35 Screenshot from HMI showing the major system components and measurement values. System pressure 18-20 bar. Mechanical pressure control keeps the H₂ stack outlet pressure at the same level as the O₂ stack inlet pressure. Water circulation only on anode side. Cooling and gas treatment are part of the system in the container.

Interfaces:

- Power input 3 phase 400 V alternating current to BOP
- Power input 3 phase 400 V alternating current to rectifier
- Water input tap water
- Heat output via cooler on the roof of the container, heat amount not measured, ambient temperature not measured
- Waste water output
- Hydrogen output venting to atmosphere during the tests (delivery to hydrogen storage tank could not be used because compressor was out of order), amount not measured
- Oxygen output venting to atmosphere, amount not measured
- Power set value: Power cannot be set, only stack current. For these experiments it is assumed that power and current will be sufficiently linear to achieve the required precision of power control by current control. Current can be set manually on HMI or via a script run on the same computer as the HMI and the data registration with (as told by manufacturer) 1s resolution

Changes to original electrolyzer to perform the tests:

As delivered by the manufacturer the BOP power could be read on a meter but not be registered. By an update of the meter and connection to the data registration the BOP AC power could also be registered with 1 Hz.

As a measurement for the rectifier input power was not available a 3 phase inductive measurement meter was installed by DLR at the rectifier input including a computer for data registration. However with some delays of this installation the meter was ready for measurement only on the last day of the time slot for these measurement, yet not calibrated. As the

measurement values of rectifier input power seemed to make no sense as compared to the rectifier output power the rectifier input power was not used in the data evaluation of these tests.

Precision of measurement:

No information on the precision of measurement of the values to be measured was provided by the manufacturer. It is not clear if the values were calibrated. It can be assumed that the precision as indicated by the individual component's manufacturer will be available. The only component which is calibrated on each day of operation is the HTO gas impurity sensor. Data registration with 1 Hz frequency.

Rectifier output power calculated from rectifier output DC current and voltage

Rectifier output DC current: the manufacturer's manuals does not indicate the precision. It states that the rectifier regulates the output current to $\pm 0.5\%$ of set point. Measurement is done by a voltage drop on a shunt ($50\text{mV}=3500\text{A}$), the voltage signal converted to $4\text{-}17.7\text{mA}=0\text{-}3100\text{ADC}$, this current signal is used as input signal to the registered data. Assuming further accuracy loss of the conversion a precision of $>\pm 0.5\%$ of set point can be assumed

Rectifier output voltage: the manufacturer's manual does not indicate the precision. It states that the rectifier regulates the output voltage to $\pm 0.5\%$ of set point. The voltage signal is converted to $4\text{-}20\text{mA}=0\text{-}14\text{VDC}$, this current signal is used as input signal to the registered data. Assuming further accuracy loss of the conversion a precision of $>\pm 0.5\%$ of set point can be assumed

BOP power: accuracy 0.5% at any point measured by Acuvim II, resolution 1 W

Time: approx. ± 2 sec. Set points and data measurement in the same computer. Absolute time of computer set when deviation exceeded 5 minutes. Delay of registration of measured data from the system can be assumed as 1-2 sec due to the processing time in the Siemens PLC.

- If the accuracy requirements as given in the testing protocols document are met, cannot be judged.

Frequency of measurement: 1 Hz

Standby state: The standby state of this electrolyser system is a cold standby. It is reached from the off-state by about 30 min of repeated nitrogen flushing of the hydrogen part of the system and water flow through the oxygen compartment. The temperature is at ambient room temperature or, if the system was operated just before, at elevated temperature.

Nominal operating point: By the manufacturer no nominal operating point was defined, only a maximum current of 3000 A (2 A/cm^2). For the purpose of this measurement we defined 2500A as the nominal current and therefore the stack power, that is reached after longer operation of the system at this current, as the nominal power. The stack temperature control setpoint is set to 65°C which was never reached because for a short stack as in this system the heat convection to ambience is too high. Therefore there is no nominal temperature in these measurements.

Boundary conditions and safety aspects for this system: A detailed controls system was set up by the manufacturer respecting cell stack health and safety for operator and system. The typical reaction of the system to exceeding a parameter was to switch off the rectifier and to release pressure in a controlled manner to the ambience with an alarm on the screen. In the final state after the problems of the system were fixed by the manufacturer the alarm that occurred repeatedly was a too high ion conductivity in the DI water in the electrolyser loop (due to ageing of the system and insufficient exchange with refreshed DI water), a pressure drop in the compressed air system (due to leaks), stack current low (if operator made mistake with current setpoint at HMI) and high oxygen in ambient air value (sensor setpoint runaway). As the hydrogen is vented to atmosphere through a pressure control valve there are no boundary conditions from the hydrogen use. Within the system the hydrogen pressure is always kept at a pressure above the oxygen pressure by a control valve setting the hydrogen outlet pressure equal to the anode water inlet pressure however limited to 1.75 bar.

Initial conditions of the system: Before starting these measurements the system was operated for approx. 30 hours. It was stored at OCV for a very long time which might have caused some degradation. According to the manufacturer's information the conditioning time of the stack should be finished after approx. 50-100 h of operation. This was reached towards the end of the set of measurements shown in this document. However the fact that the stack might not have reached fully stable conditions before these measurements is not expected to influence the dynamics of the system, only the efficiency.

3.5.2 Applying 2nd draft testing protocols (D2.4) to 50 kW PEM electrolyser system

Since the report D5.3 reporting about testing results of the 50 kW electrolyser based on the 1st draft of testing protocols D2.1 no new data could be acquired with this system because the system was not available for operation any more.

However with all data available from tests of this electrolyser it is possible to perform the data evaluations as required in D2.4 and make a prediction about the electrolyser's behavior for those parts of the testing protocols that are run differently from D2.4. The results will be shown here for exemplary tests.

3.5.2.1 Characterization test protocols

D2.4 did not describe the Basic Characterisation testing protocols in the main body of the description because it suggested that this data should be given by the manufacturer because with wrong operation the basic characterisation tests can be destructive to the system. However in the case of the 50 kW electrolyser the manufacturer has not provided this data. Therefore the previously analysed protocols are considered again.

The primary difference between the D2.1 and D2.4 version of testing protocols here is that the operating time at nominal power before starting the real test was reduced from 2 hours to 1 hour. As the DLR 50 kW electrolyser system has reached stable operation of all parameters after 1 hour of operation no matter what state has been run before that, the reduced stabilisation time should not have an influence on the subsequent test. Figure 36 shows stabilisation of system parameters after startup.

Figure 36 *System parameter stabilisation in 1 hour period after startup: cell voltages, system pressure and stack temperature are stable after that period*

3.5.2.1.1 Protocol for determination of cold start time to nominal power (D2.4, Annex E)

The difference to the description in D2.1 is minor. Therefore the same test result as in the previous tests applies here:

Cold Start Time to Nominal Power: $\tau_{cold} = 99.68$ min

Comment: the initial time between pressing the start button and increase of the stack power exhibited quite a variation in many repetitions. The minimum time achieved here was approx. 35 min so that the minimum Cold Start Time to Nominal Power was approx. 60 min.

3.5.2.1.2 Protocol for determination of start-up time from standby mode (D2.4, Annex E)

The difference of this protocol to the one in D2.1 is minor. Therefore the same result can be reported as in D5.3:

Figure 37 *Start up from standby mode. The figure shows the DC stack power. After pressing the “start production” button the HTO sensor is calibrated, then the stack current can be increased manually to nominal current. The increase should not be too fast because otherwise the differential pressure between anode and cathode or the cell voltage might exceed the allowed range and the system shuts down automatically.*

Figure 38 *Start up from standby mode showing the total system power including the BOP. After pressing the “start production” button the HTO sensor is calibrated, then the stack current can be increased manually to nominal current. Quite obviously when comparing to Figure 37 the BOP adds a non constant component which can temporarily reach a serious percentage of the nominal stack power.*

Start-up time from Standby State to Nominal Electrical Power Input: $\tau_{\text{start,standby}} = 15 \text{ min}$

Average Electrical Power Input of the system in Standby State is $P_{\text{standby}} = 10.283 \text{ kW}$ averaged over 1 hour in which the system was in nitrogen gas purging and standby state.

Deviations from test description: Before the start up examined the system was in standby only for 1 minute, not for 75 minutes as in the description. However the power consumption in nitrogen purging state and in standby is not very much different. The system total power was not controlled to meet some stability requirement, only the stack current. It was not waited until the total system power remains within $\pm 5\%$ because this is never reached. What is given as total system power is really the sum of stack power + BOP power, i.e. the efficiency of the rectifier not being 100% is not considered.

3.5.2.1.3 Protocol for identification of available range (D2.4, Annex E)

From the previous version for testing protocols to the one verified now mostly the stability criteria in this test have changed. However for the 50 kW electrolyser the system power will not be stable as indicated to $\pm 5\% P_{\text{start max}}$.

Neglecting this stability criterion and with some deviation of the order and duration of power steps as compared to the protocol the following values apply for this system:

Considering only the stack power the values are determined as

$$P_{\text{max system}} = 41.667 \text{ kW}$$

$$P_{\text{min system}} = 3.956 \text{ kW}.$$

At these values the average total system power (assuming stack power+BOP power) gives

$$P_{\max \text{ system}} = 50.515 \text{ kW}$$

$$P_{\min \text{ system}} = 29.871 \text{ kW.}$$

3.5.2.1.4 Protocol for determination of Minimum-Maximum-Dynamics (D2.4,Annex E)

There has been hardly any change in this characterisation testing protocol as compared to D2.1. The test already shown in D5.3 experiences some deviations from the testing protocol: intermediate step at nominal power, stability criteria or the full system power are not met.

The Total Response Time Minimum Power to Maximum Power $\tau_{\min \rightarrow \max}$ was approximately

$$\tau_{\min \rightarrow \max} = 85 \text{ s}$$

Total Response Time Maximum Power to Minimum Power

$$\tau_{\max \rightarrow \min} = 469 \text{ s}$$

In other experiments also a total response time Maximum Power to Minimum Power of 59 sec was achieved. The difference is due to the fact that to avoid problems with the system in too fast changes of power the operator set intermediate steps for the power change; depending on the number and duration of these intermediate steps selected the total power changes takes varying times. It was not tested what was the fastest time $\tau_{\max \rightarrow \min}$ that could be achieved reproducibly without problems with the system.

3.5.2.1.5 Protocol for Determination of Nominal-Maximum-Dynamics (D2.4, Annex E)

Figure 39 *Nominal to Maximum power. The indicated power is the stack power.*

There is hardly any difference to the tests described in D2.1. The total system stability criterion is not met due to the high BOP power fluctuations but the stack power fulfils the stability criterion of $\pm 5\% \cdot P_{\max \text{ system}}$.

Total Response Time Nominal Power to Maximum Power $\tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 23 \text{ s.}$

Total Response Time Maximum Power to Nominal Power $\tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{nom}} = 23 \text{ s}$

3.5.2.1.6 *New test:* Protocol for determination of power down to standby time and minimum duration between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent nominal power state (D2.4, Annex E)

For the Hydrogenics system pressing the “Stop” button results in immediate reduction of the rectifier current to 0 A (in data registration 1 second due to frequency of data registration) and a slow pressure release close to ambient pressure. As soon as this depress phase is finished, after

approx. 3 min, the operator can press the “reset button” to clear all errors that came in the system because of stopping. Now the system is starting with nitrogen purging cycles and reaches the standby state after approx. 45 minutes. This last phase was varying from approx. 35 min to approx. 60 min for several tests.

Deviations from the test description:

- Due to the high fluctuations in system power the defined moment with system power smaller than $P_{\text{standby}} + 5\% P_{\text{max}}$ system is never reached continuously. The BOP fluctuations are high even at standby.

Approximate results:

Time from nominal to standby power: $\tau_{\text{down_to_standby}}=1-2 \text{ sec}$

Time between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent Nominal Power state $\tau_{\text{down}\rightarrow\text{up}} = 15 \text{ min}$

3.5.2.1.7 New test: Protocol for determination of Duration of Maximum Power (D2.4, Annex E)

According to the manufacturer there should be no limitation for continuously operating the electrolyser at its maximum current of 3000 A.

During the early phase of testing the electrolyser system startup with subsequent continuous long-term operation at 3000 A was tested. At that moment there were still several problems in the electrolyser system preventing it from long-term operation in all states. These problems were eliminated later but the long-term test at maximum current was not repeated.

The test run shows several deviations from the test described in D2.4:

- System is not power-controlled but current-controlled
- No operation at nominal power for 15min before the test and for 15 min during the test
- System total power did not stabilize to $\pm 5\%$ because the BOP power shows high fluctuations and was not registered electronically; however the stack power remained within $\pm 5\% P_{\text{stack,max}}$

The maximum demonstrated operation time at maximum current for this system was 78 min (Figure 40). After this time the system experienced an emergency shutdown due to the air pressure in the pneumatic valve system being low (the system had many leaks that were fixed later).

After full operability of the system the longest test to run at 3000 A was for 21 min (see protocol dynamics nominal-maximum operation). There is no reason to believe that the operation time at 3000 A should be limited, apart from the general instability of the system at any operating point. All tests at 3000A were terminated by the operator.

Therefore it can be concluded that the duration time of maximum power τ_{max} is higher than 78 min=4680 sec.

Figure 40 Long term operation at maximum power. Stack power (41.29±0.94) kW

3.5.2.1.8 Data evaluation and identification of grid services that might be performed with this 50 kW system

Most basic characterisation values of the 50 kW system have already been determined in earlier tests and reported in D5.3. They are summarized in this table together with 2 new values that had not been requested in the first draft of testing protocols:

Parameter	Power / kW (only rectifier output power)	Power / kW (total system power)	Time / min
τ_{cold} Cold Start Time to Nominal Power			99.68 min
$\tau_{start,standby}$ Start-up time from Standby State to Nominal Electrical Power Input			15 min
$\tau_{min \rightarrow max}$ Total Response Time Minimum Power to Maximum Power			85 sec
$\tau_{max \rightarrow min}$ Total Response Time Maximum Power to Minimum Power			469s (59 sec)*
$\tau_{nom \rightarrow max}$ Total Response Time Nominal Power to Maximum Power			23 sec
$\tau_{max \rightarrow nom}$ Total Response Time Nominal Power to Maximum Power			23 sec
τ_{max} duration time of maximum power			>4680 sec
$\tau_{down \ to \ standby}$ Time from nominal to standby power			1-2 sec
$\tau_{down \rightarrow up}$ Time between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent Nominal Power state			15 min
$P_{standby}$	0 kW	10.28 kW	
$P_{cold \ standby} =$	0	1.6 kW	
P_{nom}	33.4kW	42.8 kW	
$P_{max \ system}$	41.67 kW	50.52 kW	
$P_{min \ system}$	3.96 kW	29.87 kW	

Table 6 Characteristic values of the 50 kW PEM DLR/Hydrogenics electrolyser system

*In 2 different measurements different values were obtained.

From these the power range and dynamics that is relevant for electricity grid services can be assessed and compared to the requirements of the services:

Considering stack power:
Power Range ΔP = $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} P_{\max \text{ system}} - P_{\min \text{ system}} = 37.7 \text{ kW} \\ \text{or } P_{\max \text{ system}} - P_{\text{standby}} = 41.667 \text{ kW} \end{array} \right.$

Considering total system power:
Power Range ΔP = $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} P_{\max \text{ system}} - P_{\min \text{ system}} = 20.6 \text{ kW} \\ \text{or } P_{\max \text{ system}} - P_{\text{standby}} = 40.2 \text{ kW} \end{array} \right.$

The dynamics for increasing power is depending on the selected lower and upper power state:

Time to power up τ_{up} = $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tau_{\text{cold}} + \tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 100 \text{ min} \\ \text{or } \tau_{\text{start,standby}} + \tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 15.4 \text{ min} \\ \text{or } \tau_{\text{min} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 1.4 \text{ min} \end{array} \right.$

The dynamics for decreasing power is depending on the selected lower and upper power state:

Time to power down τ_{down} = $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{min}} = 1 \text{ min} \\ \text{or } \tau_{\text{down_to_standby}} + \tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{nom}} = 48.4 \text{ min} \end{array} \right.$

Conclusion of basic characterisation and evaluation:

These values are compared to the requirements of the grid services, see Table 7: Characteristic data for grid services (Table 10 of D2.4) The system has a too small power range to be considered for grid service as a stand-alone system, only possibly via an aggregator. Taking standby or cold state as the lower power level, the dynamics of none of the services can be achieved. Within the hydrogen production range the system might be capable of performing the slower services.

Table 7: Characteristic data for grid services (Table 10 of D2.4)

Service	Power Range ΔP *	Time to power up τ_{up}	Time to power down τ_{down}
FCR	$\geq 2 \text{ MW}$	$\leq 60 \text{ sec}^{**}$	$\leq 60 \text{ sec}^{**}$
aFRR negative control	$\geq 5 \text{ MW}$	$< 133 \text{ sec}^{***}$	-
aFRR positive control	$\geq 5 \text{ MW}$	-	$< 133 \text{ sec}^{***}$
mFRR negative control	$\geq 10 \text{ MW}$	$\leq 15 \text{ min}$	-
mFRR positive control	$\geq 10 \text{ MW}$	-	$\leq 15 \text{ min}$
RR	$\geq 10 \text{ MW}$	$\leq 15 \text{ min}$	-
RR	$\geq 10 \text{ MW}$	-	$\leq 15 \text{ min}$
DSR	No general information and conditions applying to all countries		

*if system power range is too small for the service the service provision as part of a pool of an aggregator might still be possible; also in close future access permission of the 1 MW systems to the market can be expected

** the service requires up and down control from a medium power level with half the reaction time as indicated here

*** Wide variations between the countries. Compare to Annex C of D2.4

3.5.2.2 FCR testing protocol: Test method first test (D2.4, section 5.14.2.3)

As compared to the first draft of testing protocols D2.1 and the tests performed on the DLR 50 kW system based on this protocol the following changes are included in the testing protocols of D2.4:

- shorter initial time at P_{med} , reduced to 1 hour
- one of the periods at P_{up} and one of the P_{low} periods have increased duration, 30.5 min instead of 15.5. min.
- data evaluation explained in more details

As no new measurements could be performed this is to judge based on the available measurements what the results of FCR first test for this system would have been if the protocols of D2.4 had been applied.

Selection of P_{up} , P_{low} : Based on the basic characterization tests P_{low} was set by setting the stack current to 400 A. To avoid possible instabilities for longer operation at maximum power and possible high cell voltages for fast changes from medium power (and at that operation point lower stack temperature) to high power P_{up} was selected as the nominal operating point setting the current to 2500 A, not the maximum power.

Derived from this resulting from the measurements the power levels are:

$$P_{low} = 3850 \text{ W}$$

$$P_{up} = 34552 \text{ W}$$

$$P_{med} = 19201 \text{ W.}$$

Not the total electrolyser system power will be used for the grid service test but only the rectifier input power, an option permitted by the testing protocols. As can be seen in Figure 38 for the total system power during startup as compared to Figure 37 showing the stack power, the BOP power adds a highly unstable component to power which cannot be controlled. Especially when about every 12 minutes the chiller switches on, the permitted range of power deviation for all tests is exceeded. Therefore the BOP power is not considered as being part of the grid service providing power. In a real installation either a chiller would need to be integrated with a controllable and smooth power consumption, much smaller than the stack power or 2 different grid connections should be installed with only the rectifier input power being offered for grid service.

Different from the requirements of the protocols these measurements do not report the rectifier input power because only the measurement for the DC rectifier output power was accessible. So these tests assume a 100% efficiency of the rectifier which is not realistic.

Discussion of the influence of the differences between the test performed and the requirements of the testing protocol:

- shorter initial time at P_{med} , reduced to 1 hour

As shown in Figure 36 for operation at nominal power the system parameters have stabilized after 1 hour, only minor deviations after 45 min. The same will be true at medium power so that there should not be an influence on the result by the shorter initial phase. For the stability evaluation of the first period of operation at P_{med} only the last 15 minutes are considered according to the description in D2.4.

- one of the periods at P_{up} and one of the P_{low} periods have increased duration, 30.5 min instead of 15.5. min

As can be seen in the results of RR test the lower power level P_{low} is constant for an even longer time period of 1 hour. As can be seen in all the power change tests in this report the power change after a step is highest during the first minutes, decreasing afterwards because the voltage change at constant current is mostly connected to the temperature change. Temperature approaches a constant value a few minutes after a step current change. I.e. possibly an increased duration of the upper power level period might increase the power fluctuation in this period and the subsequent P_{med} period but only to a minor extend.

Results:

Figure 13: FCR First Test (Power-Time graph) that was analysed for this evaluation. Power presented here is stack power. The yellow markers show where this test deviates from the test required in D2.4. The periods A, C, E, G and I and step start 2-9 are defined in D2.4 and used for data evaluations

Data evaluation- Performance Indicators

Power stability when no grid service is provided:

Phase	Minimum power in this phase / W	Maximum power in this phase / W	Absolute value of maximum deviation from $P_{med}=19201$ W / W	Absolute maximum deviation relative to $(P_{med}-P_{low})=15350$ W / %
Phase A (here defined as 45-60 minutes after beginning of the test)	17441	17687	1760	11.5
Phase C	17150	17520	2051	13.3
Phase E	17035	17588	2166	14.1
Phase G	17425	18438	1776	11.6
Phase I	17404	18589	1797	11.7

Table 8: FCR power stability of 50 kW PEM electrolyser at P_{med}

Conclusion: the power deviation at P_{med} is very high due to the current control of the system. Almost none of the values is within the permitted range around P_{med} , all too low. A set point $I_{med}=0.5*(I_{up}-I_{low})$ does lead to precisely controlled medium power.

Power stability at P_{up} :

Phase	Minimum power in this phase / W	Maximum power in this phase / W	Absolute value of maximum deviation from $P_{up}=34552$ W / W	Absolute maximum deviation relative to $(P_{med}-P_{low})=15350$ W / %
Phase B	33565	35096	987	2.9
Phase D	33588	34630	964	6.3

The permitted range $\pm 0.05 \cdot (P_{med} - P_{low})$ is slightly exceeded.

Power stability at P_{low} :

Phase	Minimum power in this phase / W	Maximum power in this phase / W	Absolute value of maximum deviation from $P_{low} = 3850$ W / W	Absolute maximum deviation relative to $(P_{med} - P_{low}) = 15350$ W / %
Phase F	3824	3895	45	0.3
Phase H	3842	3912	62	0.4

All values in the required range of $\pm 0.05 \cdot (P_{med} - P_{low})$.

Duration of ramps up:

Figure 41 Half time and full time for FCR first test ramps 2 and 3

Step number for step up	t_m / sec	t_{full} / sec
2	20.8	41.2
4	23	43
7	31	42
9	40	52

Duration of ramps down:

Step number for step down	t_m / sec	t_{full} / sec
3	12	23
5	11	23
6	8	24
8	10	21

Performance indicator step ramp duration is the maximum of all these values, given in the table below.

Initial response time: The data registration was with 1 Hz. For all steps the power change at the next data registration point after the change of the current set point had left the previous power level continuously changing. Therefore the initial response time must be faster than 1 sec (+ 1 second between the moment the change was requested and the next system control).

3.5.2.3 Test method FCR second test (D2.4, section 5.14.2.4)

Based on the data obtained for FCR second test using the first draft testing protocol (D2.1) new data evaluation is performed. The major difference between D2.1 and D2.4 in this protocol is that based on the same grid frequency profile a maximum activation is assumed already at 0.1 Hz deviation from 50.0 Hz grid frequency. Therefore the percentage of change from the medium power is doubled. To make the new evaluation with the old data the Power levels P_{up} and P_{low} are defined differently.

The test bench did not have an externally applied power request signal but this power request was realized by a script run on the same computer as the test bench control. This script did not obey the correct time sequence. To evaluate the precision with which the system followed the setpoints the registered time sequence of the applied power request signals was used in our evaluation. Based on this power request sequence the envelope of permitted range was defined with the same rules as in D2.4 and the real power was compared to this allowed range.

However the same shortcomings as already reported in the evaluation of the tests based on the first draft of protocols continue to exist:

- The system is current controlled, the set values are defined in percentages of the nominal current; as the cell voltage increases with increasing current/temperature and even at a given current depends on the previous operation (i.e. primarily the temperature) the power setpoints are by no way precise.
- The current increase/decrease rate is limited by the manufacturer. As already the FCR first test is not passed it can be expected that the FCR second test will also not be passed.

With the assumed input power profile based on the **first draft of testing protocols (D2.1)** and taking P_{low} ("0%" in this test) as 4080 W and P_{up} ("100%" in this test) as 31166 W **91.3% of the data points are within the envelope.**

To do the data evaluation the registered data points are compared to the envelope of upper and lower limit of permitted range at each time. This envelope is given with 1 Hz. If the system data registration is slower than 1 Hz it can still be evaluated how many of the measured data points are outside the envelope.

The same data set is also taken to try to evaluate the **second draft testing protocol FCR 2nd test (D2.4)**. Of course in this case the input power signal has even more deviations from the description in the testing protocols. Comparing the required time sequence of power levels to the one set by the script protocol of the electrolyser's system control it turned out that the set values of the original profile can be taken but with time axis divided by 2.9.

Taking P_{low} ("0%" in this test) as 10852 W and P_{up} ("100%" in this test) as 24395 W **73.9% of the data points are within the envelope.** However it is noticed that the envelope is too narrow at some positions, needs to be adapted.

The average ramping rate of the systems when the set value differs by more than 1 step from the real value is: "50%" in 13.7 sec when decreasing power, "50%" in 21.2 sec when increasing power. Interestingly this value is much lower than in the first FCR test. The reason why the ramping rate in FCR first test was smaller could be that to avoid running into problems with system stability when performing large steps the operators added intermediate smaller steps and did not set the full step as target value at once. For the FCR second test no such intermediate power set steps were foreseen, because each step was smaller as given by the profile and therefore the performance was not slowed down by intermediate steps.

Like in the first FCR test the ramping rate is higher when increasing power than when decreasing power.

The major reason why data points were outside the permitted range were:

- Initial response time i.e. time until the change in power set point results in change in ramp up or down up to 3 sec
- Current control instead of power control

Figure 42 FCR second testing report compared to permitted /corridor

Figure 43 Sections of FCR second test measurement (black) and envelopes (red-orange) using the envelopes rules as defined for the D2.4 FCR second test evaluation. 73.9% of the data points are within upper and lower margin

Figure 44 Section as in Figure 43, upper curve with improved way of defining the envelope of permitted range

Result:

Performance indicator	Symbol	This system's value	TSO's requirement
Percentage of data outside the envelope for second test		26.1	0%
For power levels $P_{low} = 10.852$ kW $P_{med} = 17.623$ kW $P_{up} = 24.395$ kW			

Table 9: FCR second test performance indicators for 50 kW PEM electrolyser

FCR results for Results for 50 kW electrolyser:

Performance indicator	Symbol	This system's value	TSO's requirement
Ramp duration	t_m	40 sec	≤ 15 sec
	t_{full}	52 sec	≤ 30 sec
Stability: maximum deviation	Δ_{max}	0.141 ($P_{med} - P_{low}$)	≤ 0.05 ($P_{med} - P_{low}$)
Initial response time	t_{nit}	1-2 sec	< 1.5 sec
Percentage of data outside the envelope for second test		26.1%	0%
For power levels $P_{low} = 3.85$ kW $P_{med} = 19.201$ kW $P_{up} = 34.552$ kW			

Table 10: FCR performance indicators for 50 kW PEM electrolyser

It can easily be seen that almost all performance indicators for this system are outside the required range for FCR. To achieve a better compatibility of this system with grid service requirements the following measures would be needed:

- System control parameter should be power (rectifier input power)
- Faster system reaction by installing rectifier allowing more dynamic operation and by improved and faster system pressure controls; adaptation in the system control needed when these components have been adjusted to faster reaction
- Input port for power set value needed, feeding from the outside of this system with a verified time sequence of power levels.

3.5.2.4 aFRR testing protocols

The change from first to second draft testing protocols was that the shortest ramp time was eliminated (because not required for aFRR in any European country) and the ramps and power levels have been re-grouped. As described in D2.1 tests with ramps of different speeds were run. Also in the way of data evaluation no major changes were done from the first draft to the second draft of testing protocols. Therefore the conclusion derived from the tests based on the first draft of testing protocols and reported in D5.3 still apply.

3.5.2.4.1 aFRR negative control power: Test method part 1 Upward slow ramp protocol (D2.1 section 5.13.3.2.1.1.2 compared to D2.4 section 5.14.3.2)

It is assumed that when following the correct profile from D2.4 approximately the same results about pass/non-pass criteria will be obtained.

The electrolyser cannot be power-controlled, so the control is applied through the current. As a result there are voltage deviations throughout the stages of the protocol, which cause variations in the power. The test current set point sequence and times were written in a Script-File that is run on the same computer as the HMI and data registration and run automatically by the system after starting it. For the ramps the setpoint was changed in steps of 100 A. The times in the script file were given in seconds such that the total duration of the ramps should be correct.

Selection of P_{up} , P_{low} : Based on the basic characterization tests P_{low} was set by setting the stack current to 500 A. To avoid possible instabilities for longer operation at maximum power and possible high cell voltages for fast changes from low power (and at that operation point lower stack temperature) to high power P_{up} was selected as the nominal operating point setting the current to 2500 A, not the maximum power.

Figure 45 *Measured power graph after the initial 1 hour of operation, the power given is the stack power*

The test was performed according to the protocol guidelines, as it can be seen by the power-time graph.

When the minimum (500A) and maximum (2500A) current are applied, the approximate average power values are the following:

$P_{low} = 5100.81 \text{ W}$
 $P_{up} = 34350.79 \text{ W}$
 Consequently, $\Delta P = 29249.98 \text{ W}$ and $\epsilon_v = 1\% \Delta P = 292.5 \text{ W}$

Deviations from test description: using current control instead of power control. The periods for the set points are not exactly as required because despite the information of the manufacturer that the times in the script files are seconds this is not precise. There is no other way available for current control of the system besides script-file and manual operation. Therefore the real power value is compared to the current set point from the script that is registered in the same file to evaluate the precision of ramping up and down. The power displayed and used for data evaluation is the stack power, i.e. the rectifier output power, not rectifier input power or total system power.

Data evaluation

Compared to D2.1 the envelope of permitted values in the ramp part has become wider. For the ramps of the old protocol aFRR slow ramp this evaluation is done as an example. The faulty time scale of the test is not considered here, the comparison of real values is done to the power vs time set curve that the electrolyser has seen. In Figure 46 the relative deviation of the measured stack power values from the set points is given (relative $P_{up}-P_{low}$) and compared to the upper and lower limit of the envelope, ϵ_v and $-\epsilon_v$ as described in D2.4. The data evaluation finds 15% of the data points being outside the envelope. The deviations are highest during the ramps.

The step-down time deviation is not under examination for the partial activation curves according to the protocol and therefore not displayed in the graphs.

Figure 46 Percentage of power deviation

For faster ramps like in some of the aFRR ramps not considered here an even higher percentage of deviation from the permitted range is expected.

aFRR and mFRR control power:

Performance indicator	This system's value	TSO requirement
Percentage of data points outside the given envelope	Approx. 15%	≤5%
For power levels	$P_{low} = 5.10 \text{ kW}$	$P_{up} = 34.35 \text{ kW}$

Table 11: aFRR and mFRR performance indicators for 50 kW PEM electrolyser

The system is not within the limits required for several reasons:

- Current controlled, should be power controlled
- Set points not in perfect ramps but in steps
- Rectifier and pressure controls of the system limit the permitted speed of change
- No external power setpoint input port, internal script setpoints don't obey the required time

3.5.2.5 RR Testing protocol

The change in the test sequence from the first to the second draft of testing protocols is marginal. However the data evaluation is described in more detail in D2.4. So the previously measured data is evaluated according to the description in D2.4.

As described in D2.1 for RR the electrolyser has to change power level upon request, with no rules about the way to ramp to the new level. The new power level is maintained longer than for the other services.

3.5.2.5.1 Positive control power: Downward power conformity (D2.4, section 5.14.5.3.1)

The RR downward ramp protocol from upper power level as described in D2.1 was applied to the electrolyser:

Step	Description	Comment
1	Set system at P_{up}	
2	Wait for system power to stabilize	
3	Operate at this level for 2 hours	
4	At $t=t_1$, set system power to $P_{up}-25\%$ ($P_{up} - P_{low}$)	
5	Wait until $t=t_1+900$ seconds	
6	Keep set power for 5 minutes	
7	Set system at P_{low}	
8	Wait for system power to stabilize	
9	At $t=t_2$, set system power to $P_{up}-50\%$ ($P_{up} - P_{low}$)	
10	Wait until $t=t_2+900$ seconds	
11	Keep set power for 5 minutes	
12	Set system at P_{low}	
13	Wait for system power to stabilize	
14	At $t=t_3$, set system power to $P_{up}-75\%$ ($P_{up} - P_{low}$)	
15	Wait until $t=t_3+900$ seconds	
16	Keep set power for 5 minutes	
17	Set system at P_{low}	
18	Wait for system power to stabilize	
19	At $t=t_4$, set system power to P_{low}	
20	Wait until $t=t_4+900$ seconds	
21	Keep set power for 60 minutes	
22	At $t=t_5$, set system power to P_{up}	
23	Wait until $t=t_5+900$ seconds	
24	Keep set power for 15 minutes	
25	At $t=t_6$, set system power to P_{low}	
26	Wait until $t=t_6+900$ seconds	
27	Keep set power for 60 minutes	
28	At $t=t_7$ set power to P_{up}	
29	Wait until $t=t_7+900$ seconds	
30	Wait for system power to stabilize	
31	End of test	

Table 12: Steps of RR testing protocol

The current electrolyser cannot be power-controlled, so the control is applied through the current. As a result there are voltage deviations throughout the stages of the protocol, which cause variations in the power. Because the protocols do not specify how the system goes from unactivated to activated power level some ramps were programmed as ramps in the script-file, some as steps.

The experimental data fail to follow the protocol in the expected precision, altering the duration of each step. Thus, ramping times are considered from the real times as seen from the current set points.

To test the different ways of power change, faster and slower ramps were programmed in the script file.

Figure 47 Power graph from step 4 onwards

Selection of P_{up} , P_{low} : When the minimum (500A) and maximum (2500A) current are applied, the approximate average power values are the following:

$$P_{low} = 5058 \text{ W}$$

$$P_{up} = 33113 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Consequently, } \Delta P = 28055 \text{ W}$$

Due to long times at the lower power level, it was decided to avoid possible system instabilities and to use a power level above the minimum possible long-term current. Using the standby state of the system as the lower power level was not investigated because the basic characterization test showed that ramp up from standby and getting the system back to operation after ramping down takes too long.

Deviations from test description: using current control instead of power control. The periods for the set points are not exactly as required because despite the information of the manufacturer that the times in the script files are seconds this is not precise. There is no other way available for current control of the system besides script-file and manual operation. Therefore the real power value is compared to the current set point from the script that is registered in the same file to evaluate the precision of ramping up and down. The power displayed and used for data evaluation is the stack power, i.e. the rectifier output power, not rectifier input power or total system power. Step 27 of the protocol was interrupted and the subsequent steps could not be run. The system made an automatic shutdown.

Data evaluation

Duration of the 5 ramps down within the protocol: 278 sec, 815 sec, 31 sec, 863 sec, 860 sec, i.e. average time to reach new power level: 569 sec.

Duration of ramps down: 22 sec, 41 sec, 58 sec, 869 sec, i.e. average time to reach new power level: 247 sec.

No ramp was longer than 15 min.

Comment: for some of the ramps the input set power signal was not programmed as a step but as a ramp on purpose to test the different ways for applying the testing protocol. I.e. the times determined here for ramping up or down could be shorter for some of the ramps if desired.

Table 13: Power after the ramps after stabilization:

Min. P / W	Max. P / W	Average P / W	Target P / W	Deviation average from target / % of full activation step size
25182	25643	25328	26099	2.7
17821	17889	17874	19086	4.3
10962	11177	11097	12072	3.5
4941	5118	5047	5058	0.04
4959	5076	5008	5058	0.2

Summary data evaluation RR negative control power

The system achieves the required dynamics to reach the target values and the deviation of the average power reached from the target power is less than 5% of $P_{up} - P_{low}$ taking into account only the stack power.

Performance indicator	Symbol	This system's value	TSO's requirement
Ramp duration	t_{full}	869 s = 14.5 min	≤ 15 min
Stability: maximum deviation	Δ_{max}	0.045 ($P_{up} - P_{low}$)	≤ 0.05 ($P_{up} - P_{low}$)
Percentage of data points outside ($\pm 5\%$ ($P_{up} - P_{low}$)) during full activation phase		0%	
for power levels	$P_{low} = 5.058$ kW	$P_{up} = 33.113$ kW	

Table 14: Performance indicators for RR grid service for 50 kW PEM electrolyser

3.5.3 Conclusions

The testing protocols draft D2.4 was analysed by performing tests with a 50 kW PEM electrolyser and doing the data evaluation as described. The results of the tests are given in this document. As the tests and evaluation procedures were well applicable only few recommendations on improvements of the testing protocols were given.

The 50 kW DLR/Hydrogenics electrolyser turned out not to fulfil the requirements for grid services which is not surprising because the system was designed rather as a short stack test bench than as a quickly reacting and efficient hydrogen production system. It was seen that primarily system components like chiller and compressor as well as pressure control valves and rectifier must be designed in the right way for a system to meet the requirements if the total system power should be used for grid services. If only the rectifier input power is used for grid services the deviations from the required performance get smaller. Also the way of setting the power vs. time was inappropriate: the script file with 1 or x sec steps as input processed on the HMI computer did not well respect the time as indicated and there was no power control but only current control

available that turned out not to scale linearly with the power. However the fact that this system had several problems with respect to properly running the testing protocols helped to see which requirements to system and test bench are really needed to run the tests.

Key performance indicators of the systems as defined in D2.4 (however it must be stated here that these are approximate numbers because the tests were not run precisely as in the test protocol description):

Table 25: Key performance indicators for the 50 kW DLR/Hydrogenics PEM electrolyser

KPI	How determine from these tests	Value for this system	Target value
Dynamics: Ramp duration for step power change t_{full}	→maximum of all values t_{full} determined in the different protocols	58	10 sec (in a later definition of this target value in D2.2 the target is given as 10 (30) sec)
Stability in %:	→ (maximum of all values Δ_{max} in the different protocols)/(capacity $P_{up}-P_{low}$) *100	28%	<5%
Initial response time	→from FCR protocol	1-2 sec	<1.5 sec
Ramp precision: percentage of data points outside the defined range	→ maximum of (Percentage of data points outside the range for the ramps) for all tests	15%	0-5%
Capacity	→ minimum ($P_{up}-P_{low}$) for all tests	28.06 kW	>1MW
Reliability	Percentage of all tests following these protocols that were completed as described	Not reported	>99%

3.6 PEM electrolyser system of 1 MW

3.6.1 Description of the 1.0 MW PEM electrolyser system, the test setup, the interfaces, changes to the original electrolyser to perform the tests

DLR tried to extract the information necessary to evaluate a megawatt system from the operating data of a 1.0 MW electrolyser in Hamburg Reitbrook. In a previous project this electrolyser was tested for its dynamical operation capability with protocols somewhat similar to the ones in the QualyGridS project. Taking this data it is therefore to some extent possible to estimate how the electrolyser would have performed in the QualyGridS testing protocols. Measuring data from this electrolyser was published in ⁸, ⁹ and ¹⁰.

The electrolyser is installed at an industrial site. Its hydrogen is fed into the natural gas lines supplying the city of Hamburg. Due to legal restrictions the maximum amount of hydrogen that may be fed into this line is 2%. The natural gas flow in the connecting line is higher in winter than in summer and also subject to fluctuations during the day. However by selecting the right position of the gas grid for feed-in almost at any time the flow should be high enough to allow the maximum amount of hydrogen that can be produced by this electrolyser to be fed into the gas line.

The electrolyser's specifications are given in the table 16.

Parameter	Specification/Value
Manufacturer	Hydrogenics
Operator	Uniper
Stack Volume	0.38 m ³
Hydrogen production rate at nominal specification point	229 Nm ³ /h
Electrical power at nominal specification point	1 MW
Hydrogen production rate at overload	290 Nm ³ /h

⁸ Haubner, Bastian und Föcker, Helge und Bayer, Armin und Pitschak, Bernd und Gago, Aldo und Lettenmeier, Philipp und Voglstätter, Christopher und Smolinka, Tom (2017) „Wie kommen Wind und Sonne ins Gasnetz? Pilotprojekt zur elektrolytischen Wasserstoffherzeugung erfolgreich abgeschlossen.“ DVGW energie | wasser-praxis, pages 12-16. wvgw Wirtschafts- und Verlagsgesellschaft Gas und Wasser mbH. ISSN 1436-6134, https://elib.dlr.de/112792/1/ewp_0317_12-16_Foecker.pdf

⁹ WESpe - Wissenschaftliche Forschung zu Windwasserstoff-Energiespeichern, Teilprojekt DLR : Endbericht. P. Lettenmeier, A. Gago, K.A. Friedrich; <https://doi.org/10.2314/GBV:1029363986>; https://www.tib.eu/de/suchen?tx_tibsearch_search%5Baction%5D=download&tx_tibsearch_search%5Bcontroller%5D=Download&tx_tibsearch_search%5Bdocid%5D=TIBKAT%3A1029363986&cHash=065f43c8ab781af83b378b5e64cddeba#download-mark

¹⁰ "Kompaktes 1 MW-PEM-Wasserelektrolyse-System – Regenerativer Wasserstoff für Mobilität und Energiespeicherung (KompEISys)" Abschlussbericht, P. Lettenmeier, T. Smolinka, B. Pitschak, A. Bayer, R. Schoof, September 2016 <https://doi.org/10.2314/GBV:881196096>; https://www.tib.eu/de/suchen?tx_tibsearch_search%5Baction%5D=download&tx_tibsearch_search%5Bcontroller%5D=Download&tx_tibsearch_search%5Bdocid%5D=TIBKAT%3A881196096&cHash=856c25636ab78919422c3f182414a584#download-mark

Maximum pressure	40 bar (rel. ambient)
Maximum operating pressure	30 bar (rel. ambient)
Operating temperature	50-80°C
Hydrogen purity	>99.99%
System response (minimum load to 1 MW)	<30 sec
Energy consumption	4.0-5.2 kWh/Nm ³
Cell area	>1500 cm ²
Number of cells	212
Hydrogen Quality	>99.99%

Table 36: Specifications of the field test system in Hamburg Reitbrook⁸

The system is set up almost in the same way as the 50 kW electrolyser at DLR (because the idea of the previous project was to have the smaller electrolyser at DLR with the same performance characteristics to perform degradation tests in more harsh conditions that would not be applied to an expensive full scale electrolyser). The only difference is that the DLR system had at the beginning of operation an additional Deoxo device for hydrogen purification for automotive use; the Reitbrook electrolyser only uses a drying system and by that achieves sufficient purity to feed into the natural gas. Sensors and a gas chromatograph test water, oxygen and nitrogen impurities in hydrogen.

The nominal operating point of the system is 1 MW, however an overload to 1.5 MW is possible and without time restrictions. The system control is set up in such a way that the power is controlled, however it is not clear if the control value is the total system power or the stack power. The system was not layed out for maximum dynamics but for the sake of improved efficiency has a somewhat limited dynamics¹¹.

¹¹ Oral information Hydrogenics

Figure 48 Stack and system of Hydrogenics system in Hamburg Reitbrook.
Reproduced from presentation Jan Vaes, "Hydrogen generators for energy"

**storage and industrial application”, World of Energy Solutions Stuttgart
October 10 2016¹²**

Figure 49 Outside view of the installation in Hamburg Reitbrook

All pictures reproduced from ¹³.

3.6.2 Applying 2nd draft testing protocols (D2.4) to 1.0 MW PEM electrolyser system

3.6.2.1 Basic characterization (D2.4 5.14.1)

D2.4 did not describe the Basic Characterisation testing protocols in the main body of the description because it suggested that this data should be given by the manufacturer because with wrong operation the basic characterisation tests can be destructive to the system. However in the case of our 1 MW electrolyser we do not have access to the information given by the manufacturer. Therefore the available data run in a similar way as described in the QualyGridS testing protocols is considered.

3.6.2.1.1 Protocol for determination of cold start time to nominal power (D2.4 Annex E)

Starting from a cold standby state, non-pressurized, the system has to do nitrogen purges, then start to build up pressure, blow out the nitrogen and heat up, then it is getting ready for power increase. In the start evaluated the first power set level after the start was below the nominal power, so that the time for the ramp from this power level to nominal power was added. Once the nominal power is reached the system power remains within the $\pm 5\%$ limits.

Cold start time to nominal power $\tau_{cold} = 99 \text{ min}$

It is not clear from the data available if any of the phases of purging with nitrogen and filling with H_2 could be done shorter than in this single case.

- Average Electrical Power Input of the system in cold standby state:

$$P_{cold \text{ standby}} = 1.6 \text{ kW}$$

¹² (file Hydrogenics_WES2016_c4.1_1_vaes_script.pdf)

¹³ Haubner, Bastian und Föcker, Helge und Bayer, Armin und Pitschak, Bernd und Gago, Aldo und Lettenmeier, Philipp und Voglstätter, Christopher und Smolinka, Tom (2017) Wie kommen Wind und Sonne ins Gasnetz? Pilotprojekt zur elektrolytischen Wasserstoffherzeugung erfolgreich abgeschlossen. DVGW energie | wasser-praxis, Seiten 12-16. wvgw Wirtschafts- und Verlagsgesellschaft Gas und Wasser mbH. ISSN 1436-6134; https://elib.dlr.de/112792/1/ewp_0317_12-16_Foecker.pdf

3.6.2.1.2 Protocol for determination of start-up time from standby mode (D2.4 Annex E)

The nominal power for the complete system is $P_{nom, system}$ 1076 kW; at that stage the nominal power for the stack is $P_{nom, stack}$.

Two different modes of hot standby were applied. The first mode was to turn the stack power to zero and keep the gases in the system until the temperature or the pressure were dropping below a predefined level. Then the system was switched on for several minutes with venting the produced gases, then stack power to zero again. The system power when stack power was zero was approx. 70 kW and approx. 210 kW while being switched on to increase temperature. Therefore at average the system power during standby was approx. 150 kW varying between 70 kW and 210 kW.

Later in the project hot standby was realized by operation at approx. 280.4 kW system power which is in fact the lowest power for continuous operation and hydrogen production. The system power variation in this state was quite low. The startup from this hot standby to nominal power is done in 27 sec. Figure 50 shows this startup, however not to nominal but to maximum power.

Figure 50 Standby and startup ramp

- Start-up time from Standby State to Nominal Electrical Power Input: $\tau_{start, standby} = 27 \text{ sec}$
- Average Electrical Power Input of the system in Standby State:
 $P_{standby, system} = 280.4 \pm 3.6 \text{ kW}$ for the system power and
 $P_{standby, stack} = 259.6 \pm 3.6 \text{ kW}$ for the stack power

3.6.2.1.3 Protocol for determination of available range (D2.4 Annex E)

For the test displayed in Figure 51 the maximum system power is $1492 \pm 16 \text{ kW}$, the minimum system power (at hot standby) is $282 \pm 5 \text{ kW}$. However different from the description in D2.4 Annex E the power levels were not maintained for 1 hour each. It was demonstrated in other measurements that both power levels can be maintained for 1 hour. The power stability during these periods is sufficient.

Different from this test the maximum system power was 1533 kW in other tests.

- The average Electrical Power Input of the system at maximum power level $P_{max, system} = 1533 \text{ kW}$
- The average Electrical Power Input of the system at 0 or minimum hydrogen output continuously operable: $P_{min, system} = 282 \text{ kW}$

3.6.2.1.4 Protocol for determination of Minimum-Maximum-Dynamics (D2.4 Annex E)

Data in the order as described in D2.4 and with the exact durations is not available. However Figure 51 shows a comparable power profile.

- The Total Response Time Minimum Power to Maximum Power $\tau_{\min \rightarrow \max} = 37 \text{ sec}$
- The Total Response Time Maximum Power to Minimum Power $\tau_{\max \rightarrow \min} = 20 \text{ sec}$

However in this test the power level assumed as maximum power is below the demonstrated maximum power of the system, i.e. the real times between minimum and maximum power should be a little bit longer.

Figure 51 Power profile for determining minimum-maximum dynamics

3.6.2.1.5 Protocol for Determination of Nominal-Maximum-Dynamics (D2.4 Annex E)

The values were evaluated from a profile similar to the one required for determination of nominal-maximum-Dynamics..

- The Total Response Time Nominal Power to Maximum Power $\tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 12 \text{ sec}$
- The Total Response Time Maximum Power to Nominal Power $\tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{nom}} = 9 \text{ sec}$

3.6.2.1.6 Protocol for determination of power down to standby time and minimum duration between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent nominal power state (D2.4 Annex E)

The measurement evaluated here shows some variation in power levels compared to the required profile. However the numbers can be extrapolated from the available system data.

Time from nominal to standby state: $\tau_{\text{down_to_standby}} = 11 \text{ sec}$

From the data it can only be estimated when the standby state is reached by the system and a restart is possible.

- Time between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent Nominal Power state $\tau_{\text{down} \rightarrow \text{up}} = 304 \text{ sec}$

The available data and information is not sufficient to judge if this is the minimum time to restart and if the time to restart will be the same for every run of the system.

3.6.2.1.7 New test: Protocol for Determination of Duration of maximum power

The system has overload capability i.e. the test can be run.

Maximum power operation was tested. The maximum time demonstrated in the data available to us was more than 6 hours:

- The duration time of maximum power is $\tau_{\max} > 240 \text{ min}$

3.6.2.1.8 Data evaluation and identification of grid services that might be performed with this 1 MW system

The characterization of the system by power values and characteristic times in the previous sections is summarized in the table 17. It must be stated that the values are in part estimated because not exactly the required profile were used. Also no repetition of the measurement was done, i.e. it is not clear, if the values always turn out the same.

Parameter	Power / kW (only rectifier output power)	Power / kW (total system output power)	Time / min
τ_{cold} Cold Start Time to Nominal Power			99 min
$\tau_{\text{start,standby}}$ Start-up time from Standby State to Nominal Electrical Power Input			27 sec
$\tau_{\text{min} \rightarrow \text{max}}$ Total Response Time Minimum Power to Maximum Power			37 s
$\tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{min}}$ Total Response Time Maximum Power to Minimum Power			20 sec
$\tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}}$ Total Response Time Nominal Power to Maximum Power			12 s
$\tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{nom}}$ Total Response Time Maximum Power to Nominal Power			9 s
τ_{max} duration time of maximum power			>>240 min
$\tau_{\text{down_to_standby}}$ Time from nominal to standby state			11 sec
$\tau_{\text{down} \rightarrow \text{up}}$ Time between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent Nominal Power state			304 sec
P_{standby}	260 kW	280.4 kW	
$P_{\text{cold standby}} =$	0	1.6 kW	
P_{nom}	1048 kW	1076 kW	
$P_{\text{max system}}$	1500 kW	1533 kW	
$P_{\text{min system}}$	260 kW	282 kW	

Table 27 Characteristic values of Hydrogenics Reitbrook 1 MW PEM electrolyser system

With this according to the testing protocol evaluation the characteristic numbers relevant for deciding about which grid service could be tested are determined:

$$\text{Power Range } \Delta P = 1250 \text{ kW for fast start} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} P_{\text{max system}} - P_{\text{min system}} = 1251 \text{ kW} \\ \text{or } P_{\text{max system}} - P_{\text{standby}} = 1252.6 \text{ kW} \\ \text{or } P_{\text{max system}} - P_{\text{cold-standby}} = 1531.4 \text{ kW} \end{array} \right.$$

The dynamics for increasing power is depending on the selected lower and upper power state:

$$\text{Time to power up } \tau_{\text{up}} = \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tau_{\text{cold}} + \tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 99 \text{ min} + 12 \text{ sec} = 5952 \text{ sec} \\ \text{or } \tau_{\text{start,standby}} + \tau_{\text{nom} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 39 \text{ sec} \\ \text{or } \tau_{\text{min} \rightarrow \text{max}} = 37 \text{ sec} \end{array} \right.$$

The dynamics for decreasing power is depending on the selected lower and upper power state:

$$\text{Time to power down } \tau_{\text{down}} = \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{min}} = 20 \text{ sec} \\ \tau_{\text{down_to_standby}} + \tau_{\text{max} \rightarrow \text{nom}} = 11 \text{ sec} + 9 \text{ sec} = 20 \text{ sec} \end{array} \right.$$

Conclusion of basic characterisation and evaluation:

These values are compared to the requirements of the grid services, see Table 18.

- The system has a too small power range to be considered for grid service as a stand-alone system, only possibly via an aggregator. This applies to using the total system power or using the rectifier input power. The difference between rectifier power and total power is not very big and the power stability at a certain level is good
- Taking cold standby state as the lower power level, the dynamics of none of the services can be achieved.
- Taking standby state as the lower power level, the system might be capable of performing all services.
- Within the hydrogen production range the system might be capable of performing all services.

Table 18: Characteristic data for grid services (Table 10 of D2.4)

Service	Power Range ΔP *	Time to power up τ_{up}	Time to power down τ_{down}
FCR	≥ 2 MW	≤ 60 sec**	≤ 60 sec**
aFRR negative control	≥ 5 MW	< 133 sec***	-
aFRR positive control	≥ 5 MW	-	< 133 sec***
mFRR negative control	≥ 10 MW	≤ 15 min	-
mFRR positive control	≥ 10 MW	-	≤ 15 min
RR	≥ 10 MW	≤ 15 min	-
RR	≥ 10 MW	-	≤ 15 min
DSR	No general information and conditions applying to all countries		

*if system power range is too small for the service, the service provision as part of a pool of an aggregator might still be possible; also in close future access permission of the 1 MW systems to the market can be expected.

**the service requires up and down control from a medium power level with half the reaction time as indicated here

*** Wide variations between the countries. Compare to Annex C

3.6.2.2 FCR testing protocol: Test method first test

FCR first test is a step profile. An initial longer phase at medium power is temporarily interrupted by switching to a high and later to a low power level. From the data available displaying similar profiles the power levels are selected:

P_{med} 968 kW system power

P_{up} 1492 kW system power

Consequently $P_{low} = P_{med} - (P_{up} - P_{med}) = 444$ kW system power

Alternatively, if the rectifier input power/stack power is to be taken for grid service the power levels are:

P_{med} 943 kW stack power

P_{up} 1463 kW stack power

Consequently $P_{low} = P_{med} - (P_{up} - P_{med}) = 423$ kW system power

It is noted however from the data that the set value for the system is the value for the stack power, but the real measured stack power is always higher than the set value. Therefore even if the system with this control implemented should meet the FCR requirements it would still be better to have the control based on the parameter which is the really relevant requested value for grid service, the total system power.

Figure 52 shows the requested power level sequence for FCR first test, Figure 53 shows parts of two different tests run on the 1 MW electrolyser resembling the sequence in FCR first test from which the suitability of the system to perform FCR first test can be estimated.

Figure 52 FCR 1st test of QualyGridS testing protocols D2.4

Figure 53 Two step testing protocols very similar to FCR 1st test protocol of QualyGridS P_{med} : set value 900 kW, stack power average (943±40) kW. P_{up} : set value 1400 kW, stack power average (1463±27) kW. P_{low} : set value 400 kW, stack power average (415±8) kW.

Test evaluation:

Power stability at P_{med} : In all phases at P_{med} , starting evaluation 30 seconds after the previous step trigger

	System power	Stack power
Deviation rel. ($P_{med}-P_{low}$)	5.3%	7.7%

Power stability at P_{up} :

	System power	Stack power
Deviation rel. ($P_{med}-P_{low}$)	5.7 %	5.1 %

Power stability at P_{low} :

	System power	Stack power
Deviation rel. ($P_{med}-P_{low}$)	1.7 %	1.5 %

KPI power stability:

	System power	Stack power
Maximum value $\Delta_{max} =$	30 kW	25 kW
Required value $\leq 0.05(P_{med}-P_{low})$	26.2 kW	26 kW

Duration of ramps up:

Duration ramps up

	System power ramps	Stack power ramps
t_m	10 sec	10 sec
t_{full}	18 sec	18 sec

In the normal FCR first test protocol there are 4 up ramps to be evaluated. With the data available here there is only 1 ramp of the step height ($P_{med}-P_{low}$).

Duration ramps down

	System power ramps	Stack power ramps
t_m	6 sec and 7 sec	6 sec and 7 sec
t_{full}	11 sec and 10 sec	11 sec and 10 sec

Different from the 4 ramps down in the original protocol only 2 ramps could be analysed with the available data.

KPI step ramp duration:

Maximum of t_m = 10 sec Required value: 15 sec
Maximum of t_{full} = 18 sec Required value: 30 sec

Initial response time:

As the data acquisition rate was only 1 Hz the determination of this value is not very precise.
Observed initial response time 2 ± 1 sec Required value ≤ 1.5 sec

FCR second test:

For this electrolyser system no power profile comparable to the one in FCR second test was run. Therefore an evaluation is not possible

Summary evaluation:

The table summarizes the results for FCR test comparing the parameters to requirements for taking the electrolyser system power for FCR grid service:

Table 49: FCR performance indicators for total system power for 1 MW PEM electrolyser

Performance indicator	Symbol	This system's value	TSO's requirement
Ramp duration	t_m	10 sec	≤ 15 sec*
	t_{full}	18 sec	≤ 30 sec
Stability: maximum deviation	Δ_{max}	30 kW	$\leq 0.05 (P_{med}-P_{low})=$ 26.2 kW
Initial response time	t_{init}	2 ± 1 sec	≤ 1.5 sec **
Percentage of data points outside the envelope for second test		Not measured	0%
for power levels	$P_{low}= 444$ kW	$P_{med}= 968$ kW	$P_{up}= 1492$ kW

*Different from other countries requirements for Fingrid FCR-D, FCR-N and FCR-D in Norway and FCR-D in Denmark D2 Zone , $t_m \leq 5$ sec is required. FCR-D in Norway and Denmark D2 zone is only for positive control power i.e. for electrolyzers/load for power reduction upon request.

** Requirement varying between the countries

The table summarizes the results for FCR test comparing the parameters to requirements for taking the electrolyser rectifier input power/stack power for FCR grid service:

Table 20: FCR performance indicators for stack power (without BOP) for 1 MW PEM electrolyser

Performance indicator	Symbol	This system's value	TSO's requirement
Ramp duration	t_m	10 sec	≤ 15 sec*
	t_{full}	18 sec	≤ 30 sec
Stability: maximum deviation	Δ_{max}	26 kW	$\leq 0.05 (P_{med}-P_{low})=$ 26.2 kW
Initial response time	t_{init}	2 ± 1 sec	≤ 1.5 sec **
Percentage of data points outside the envelope for second test		Not measured	0%
for power levels	$P_{low}= 423$ kW	$P_{med}= 943$ kW	$P_{up}= 1463$ kW

Comment on the system’s performance with respect to FCR:

The 1MW electrolyser system shows sufficient dynamics considering the ramp durations to perform FCR.

However the initial response time is longer than requested in some European countries, primarily due to the low frequency of data acquisition and control. Initial response time of 1.5 sec is however requested only in few countries. Some countries require 2 sec, others permit a delay if only the 50% value of the ramp is achieved.

Power stability (including BOP) of the electrolyser system is much better than for smaller systems. However it is still at the limit to stay within the ranges defined for FCR. This is because the system seems not to exactly control the rectifier input or system power. It could be that the stack input DC power is controlled (i.e. rectifier output power). This causes a, yet small, deviation from the required precision.

3.6.2.3 aFRR and mFRR testing protocols

aFRR and mFRR tests are all ramp protocols analysing the precision of running the ramps and the precision and stability of the constant phases in-between. Ramps of varying speed were run with the 1 MW electrolyser however none with exactly the ramp speed and profile as required by the QualyGridS testing protocols. Still evaluation of the available ramp tests can give an estimate of the performance the 1MW system might have if run in QualyGridS profiles.

3.6.2.4 Negative control power: Upward ramp protocol

Ramp profiles similar to the required profiles of mFRR negative control power were run with the 1 MW system. The ramp duration here is 12 min as compared to 10 min in the required protocol. The constant power level at P_{low} was maintained for the required 60 min, however the required 60 min at P_{up} were not demonstrated in this profile.

Figure 54 Protocol mFRR as defined in D2.4 testing protocols

Data evaluation

The sections of ramp and the sections with constant power are analysed and compared to the permitted range as described in D2.4. The full system power including BOP was used for the analysis.

The set power profiles for the ramps were resolved into small steps. For this rather slow ramp profile the step approximation was almost sufficient, however for a faster ramp more intermediate steps would be necessary.

Table 21: mFRR performance indicators for total system power for 1 MW PEM electrolyser

Performance indicator	Symbol	This system's value	TSO's requirement
Percentage of data points outside the range for constant power periods		0 %	≤ 5%
Percentage of data points outside the range for the ramps		1.85 %	≤ 5%
for power levels		$P_{low} = 300.8 \text{ kW}$	$P_{up} = 1499 \text{ kW}$

This means that according to these tests the system should be able to perform mFRR negative control power.

3.6.2.5 aFRR and mFRR testing protocols

aFRR ramps are faster than for mFRR. Tests with fast ramp profiles were not available in the data analysed of the 1MW electrolyser. Looking at the FCR test results the system should be fast enough for running fast ramps, however the system control for the ramp profile must be adapted.

3.6.2.6 RR Testing protocol

RR tests were not run for the 1 MW system however based on the performance in FCR-like tests, on FRR-like tests and in the basic characterisation an estimate about the system's behaviour in RR tests can be given. Requirements for RR are less challenging than for FCR and FRR. The ramp speed following a power step signal was demonstrated in FCR. It was fast enough. Also the stability at all power levels tested was sufficiently good. Long enough operation times at various power levels were demonstrated in the data analysed. I.e. apart from the capacity (the difference between maximum and minimum power) RR protocols can be done by this electrolyser.

3.6.3 Learnings for real size Megawatt electrolyzers

Data registration and also control time intervals for this system are not fast enough for FCR service. Most installations have control and data registration steps with a maximum frequency of 1 Hz. To meet the FCR initial response time of 1.5 seconds a control step of less than 1 second would be preferential and data registration must be clearly with steps below 1 second.

Even though PEM electrolyzers can better stay in a standby state without nitrogen flushing therefore being able to provide usable hydrogen immediately after the start, a service that requires extended times at standby is not favourable. For this electrolyser two alternative ways of controlling the standby state were seen: in one case the electrolyser was switching to operation with venting the produced hydrogen in regular intervals to stabilize the temperature, pressure and gas composition in the system. Such an operation does not meet the requirements of power stability at the lower power level. In the other case the electrolyser was continuously operated at a very low power level venting the produced gas; in this case the power stability is sufficient. However in both cases it is not economic to operate the electrolyser in standby for extended time.

Also starting having the electrolyser in off state (cold and nitrogen flushed) starting procedure takes too long, is not meeting any ramp requirements and the period until usable hydrogen is produced (low nitrogen content) is too long. So such an operation mode would only be possible for services with long preparation times and subsequent long operation. However as shown in the project's economic evaluation due to the high CAPEX of electrolyzers the electrolyser should have as many operating hours per year as possible.

Therefore the only reasonable way of operating today's PEM electrolyzers for grid services requiring a low power as starting state and high power when the service is activated will be to

continuously operate the electrolyser at a low power, low hydrogen production rate state and to increase to maximum power when the service is activated.

Concerning future developments it would be good to have a low CAPEX electrolyser that can quickly and with a continuous ramp start to operation when being activated. Also the power stability of the investigated system is still exceeding the permitted range by a small amount, i.e. system power or rectifier input power control has to be somewhat improved.

Restrictions of the application case of feeding hydrogen into the gas grid did not have any impact on the operation of the electrolyser. However the economic situation of this application was considered very unfavourable by the owner so that the electrolyser system was taken out of operation after only a short testing period.

It must also be emphasized that the 1 MW system was not explicitly designed to meet the requirements of all grid services that were tested. We assume that a PEM electrolyser system designed in the right way for a given application should be capable to perform any grid service of those in protocols of D2.4. We cannot see any technical restriction that might not be solved.

3.6.4 Conclusions

The testing protocols draft D2.4 was analysed by using similar data from a 1 MW PEM electrolyser and doing the data evaluation as described. The results of the tests are given in this document. As the evaluation procedures were well applicable only few recommendations on improvements of the testing protocols were given.

The 1 MW system is a highly efficient and power controlled system. It was much closer to the requirements of grid services than the 50 kW PEM electrolyser. Only some minor deviations from the required power stability and an initial response that cannot always meet the fastest requirements because the frequency of data measurement and control in that case should be further increased were identified. This shows that if modern PEM electrolyser systems are designed for grid service application they can perform them.

Key performance indicators of the systems as defined in D2.4 (however it must be stated here that these are approximate numbers because the tests were not run precisely as in the test protocol description):

Table 22: Key performance indicators for the 1 MW Uniper/Hydrogenics PEM electrolyser

KPI	How determine from these tests	Value for this system	Target value
Dynamics: Ramp duration for step power change t_{full}	→ maximum of all values t_{full} determined in the different protocols	18 sec	10 sec (in a later definition of this target value in D2.2 the target is given as 10 (30) sec)
Stability in %:	→ (maximum of all values Δ_{max} in the different protocols)/(capacity $P_{up}-P_{low}$) *100	3.8 %	<5%
Initial response time	→ from FCR protocol	2±1 sec	<1.5 sec
Ramp precision: percentage of data points outside the defined range	→ maximum of (Percentage of data points outside the range for the ramps) for all tests	1.85	0-5%
Capacity	→ minimum ($P_{up}-P_{low}$) for all tests	1.040 MW	>1MW
Reliability	Percentage of all tests following these protocols that were completed as described	No information available	>99%

4 Additional general comments

Test bench setup:

It turned out to be important that the input signal of the power level to be set is decoupled from the electrolyser system and that the time series of this input signal is tested before connecting it to the electrolyser. The electrolyser system should have a power setting input port and an internal power control that preferentially controls the total system power including the BOP.

For comparability of various setups of systems and varying environmental conditions all input and output of heat, flows and electricity should be registered which however will be difficult to realize in case of heat transfer to the atmosphere. If only a core system not including the real industrial cooling and other major power-consuming components this data acquisition at the interfaces is especially important.

Reproducibility:

In the tests reported in this report especially in the basic characterisation section some results showed a rather large range. This is because the operators performing the tests were not very familiar with the system yet and not much information from the manufacturer available and due to maloperation and to be careful not to cause incidents like shutdown the tests were never run exactly in the same way. It would be useful to repeat the basic characterisation tests several times trying to approach a desired value, e.g. a fast power change. When the extreme value is found it should be tested at least 3 times to verify reproducibility. However the basic characterisation tests are not necessarily tests exclusively relating to the grid service operation and therefore the values needed here should rather be provided by the manufacturer.

For the grid service testing protocols a good reproducibility is assumed because each protocol starts with reaching constant and stable conditions before always the same power profile is applied. It is expected that no big deviations of the electrolyser behaviour should be in several tries.

Due to the repetitive nature of all the testing protocols a certain test of reproducibility is also done within the test. Ramps or steps are always repeated with small deviation. If for the different parts within a test no reproducibility is achieved it is advisable to repeat the entire test.

Reliability:

According to JRC's [JRC2018] definition reliability is "the ability of an item to perform a required function under stated conditions for a stated period of time."

To judge the reliability, all tries of performing a grid service protocol should be reported including the less successful ones to show the range of operation of the system and if relevant the reason for failure. If a system performs all tests from these protocols enough data is available to get an estimate on reliability.

According to information from the experts within the project TSOs require a high reliability in the range of 99%.

For the 50 kW system the reliability of the system during the testing period was rather low because it turned out that some technical configuration still had to be changed to achieve a stable performance of the system. For the 1 MW electrolyser we do not have access to information about reliability.

How get from small systems tested to prediction of Megawatt system behaviour:

The DLR 50 kW system had the same stack as the Hamburg Reitbrook 1 MW electrolyser, only as short stack. It was also mostly operated in the same way with the same parameters and system concept. However the exact selection of BOP components was of course different and as these have a major influence on parameters

like dynamics and power stability the results from the 50 kW electrolyser cannot be extrapolated to 1 MW. The relative part of the BOP power is much smaller for the 1 MW system, the power control further smoothens the power stability and the dynamics is higher with more rapid ramps¹⁴ (see Appendix B, paper R. Reissner et al from European fuel cell forum 2020). Also it has a hot standby-state that the 50 kW electrolyser does not have.

The performance indicators of the small and the large system differ quite a bit (Table 15 and Table 22).

So if tests are to be run with smaller electrolyzers with the results being relevant for large scale electrolyzers either the system components for smaller systems must be selected with the same behaviour as for the larger ones (which is probably not available on the market) or the tests must be run collecting all available data of the system and then applying simulation models for electrolyser system behaviour introducing the behaviour of the finally selected BOP components.

Are important grid services missing?

The most important characteristics of most grid services available on the European market should be covered by these tests. Since the first draft D2.1 that was based on an overview of European grid services in August 2017 (D1.1) most countries have updated their prequalification procedures. These updates as well as the correction of some misunderstandings on the 2017 situation are corrected in the presently (December 2019) existing draft of the updated testing protocols D2.4. Some of the British services and prequalification requirements might not be covered, however these are right now in a major revision and it is not yet clear what prequalifications will be requested in the future. DSO, Demand side management and Peer to Peer services that can also be performed by electrolyzers are not clearly defined, information is hardly available and there is no unification in Europe. However for more or less all services the requirement for the electrolyser will be to increase or decrease power based on a given schedule and this property is tested with the testing protocols in their present (or updated) shape. A service that is expected to come into the market is Inertia provision to the grid. With less and less rotating masses due to conventional power plants being shut down the less persistent renewable energies cause a faster and nervous behavior of the grid. For Inertia service a very fast reaction and a very short duration of the required power change of the system is needed. Moreover preferentially power production units should provide inertial service, not power consumers. So from today's point of view inertia service will hardly be provided by an electrolyser system.

Comments about the second draft testing protocols D2.4

[Absolute value of maximum deviation from \$P_{med}\$, \$P_{low}\$ and \$P_{up}\$ at their respective periods are considered for KPI power stability](#)

This protocol is characterised by the power stability and the capacity to modify power fast enough thus, if even the smallest power deviation outside $\pm 5\%(P_{med}-P_{low})$ is not allowed, it makes sense to include the three of them as KPI in relation to power stability and to consider the biggest deviation instead of an average value

Comment about the basic characterization protocol for determination of power down to standby time and minimum duration between reaching standby state and reaching the subsequent nominal power state: More useful information for grid services would be the time between the moment when nominal power is left to go to standby and the

¹⁴ R. Reissner, J. Buerkle, P. Lettenmeier, A.S. Gago, K.A. Friedrich, „Qualifying Tests of Electrolyzers for Grid Services – System Behaviour and Scalability”, Proceedings of EFCF 2019, 2-5 July 2019, Lucerne, Switzerland

moment when nominal power is reached again. As it is described now in the protocol the long time for nitrogen flushing of the system is not included in these numbers.

5 Bibliography

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